

Final report of the Master's thesis carried
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Managerial summary

The objective of this Master's thesis, conducted in start-up mode, is to answer the following question:

How to create and develop a model of Lab that is a supportive environment for the development of more sustainable lifestyle solutions?

To do so, we have done a first large survey on third -places, then a deeper one on open models, in parallel to the field study and design and engineering aspects. This second survey really opened us up to the world of the contribution economy, and allowed us to create an innovative governance model and business model.

The result is a real ecosystem built on a virtuous circle. It consists firstly of the non profit Foundation OKA, which aims to support the ecosystem by providing standards and technical and legal tools to share knowledge. Second, there are the OKA Labs, which aim to provide a model of physical places for students to develop and implement sustainable projects. Finally, there are the OKA brands, which offer services based on the systems contained in the knowledge base and take economic and legal responsibility for them.

Open models are still young and models based on the contribution economy are still little known and do not exploit its full potential. Our innovation lies in the realization of open hardware, as well as in the provision of Labs, built from scratch and resulting from student projects.

Keywords: open models, contribution economy, knowledge, students

Foreword

Choosing a Master's thesis in start-up mode was an obvious choice for our group. Léon had already started to imagine OKA during his Bachelor thesis and he quickly convinced three other people to create the group. The project as it is now was mainly formed during the open models monitoring, and from there the decisions were taken naturally. The contribution economy and the benefits it implies naturally aligned with our values.

Thus, the goal of the work was from the beginning more than the realization of a TM, and even later, more than the creation of a start-up. In order to realize a real sustainable service, we think that it is more than just bringing a new ecological product. The market in which this one fits is no longer sustainable enough, and more globally the economic cycle in which we find ourselves today is perhaps showing its weakness. Being in a school of innovation, we embarked on a real radical innovation and we rethought the model in which it would take place. We imagined a more sustainable ecosystem, including green products, interactions open to all without discrimination, and a lucrative BM possible for everyone.

This work is thus in the context of the contribution economy, and of course, such systems already exist. There is for example Ideavox, a third-place in Vernier which also comes from a Foundation and represents a replicable model of future third-places. Our innovation, however, lies in the realization of open hardware, the provision of Labs, the fact of building them from scratch and the co-construction of them issuing from student projects.

The counterpart of the preparation of the creation of such an ecosystem, is that we cannot present after only one year a really achieved project. There are still a lot of details to be worked out, such as whether a

scholarship would be possible for the students or what transportation would be possible to bring them to our OKA Lab. There is still a lot of work ahead of us and certainly many readjustments.

We also encountered several difficulties during the work, the main one being that each of the members found a job with different hours (the Master's work being only 50%). We tried to solve this problem by using communication tools, and we set up a system of to-do lists on LeanTime so that everyone could follow what the others were doing.

In order to carry out this work, we adopted an agile approach and thus did not quite follow the methodology learned during our first year of training at Innokick (more focused on the realization of mandates than start-ups according to us). We spent a lot of time on monitoring and studying the field and went back and forth between the field and the theory. The world of open models being very little known, there was a real challenge to understand these models ourselves before launching into the creation of a project in this field. We then developed a governance model and a BM. At the same time, we looked at design and engineering aspects.

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List of abbreviations

BM	Business model
BMC	Business model canvas
LL	Living Lab
TM	Master thesis
VPC	Value proposition canvas
WP	Work package
GPL	GNU General Public Licence
OSI	Open Source Initiative

OKA is the association created in mid-May 2022 especially for this Master thesis (TM).

OKA aims to create a model of ecological research centre focused on the development of sustainable solutions, by bringing together the knowledge and skills of students from different fields and schools. This research centre would be more than an open-air Living Lab (LL) where students and stakeholders could live, exchange and develop their solutions. Indeed, every project will have to correspond to the criterias of sustainability and ethics. Furthermore, we want to set up a *library of Alexandria* by documenting all the knowledge and projects in order to constitute an open database. This database would be presented in the form of a platform that would allow easy and efficient access to useful and applicable knowledge for all.

The founding members are the members of the TM group (Léon, Gwenaëlle, Samantha and Simone), as well as the owner of the land in Portugal.

These people are also part of the association because this project is more than a TM for the four of us. It is a big project on which various people will work and intervene. It is thus a question in this document of well defining the limits of what we will carry out in this TM. The project will continue after the end of our TM.

In order to create the association, in summer 2021 we held a General Assembly (see appendix I), created the statutes (see Appendix II), registered it in the commercial register (see appendix III). Then we opened a bank account (see appendix IV).

We also went to two congresses between 18 and 23 September 2021 that took place in Lugano and Turino, where we made many contacts and conducted expert interviews. In advance, we created a first version of the website and a business card, and distributed it widely for these events (appendix V).

Meanings of OKA

OKA means a “house for the community” in Tupi Guaraní language (Brazilian indigenous language).

In addition, the acronym OKA also stands for «Open Knowledge Association». That is why we have chosen this word to name the association we created last year, and more generally the ecosystem of the project.

The team

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Léon Andrey Da Silva

Conception & design engineer

Simone Quirici

Internet & Communication engineer

Samantha Ingold

Tourism & management

Context

The evolution of the society is based on the transfer of knowledge and the development of new technologies. (Arber, 2009)

In fact, in the history of humanity, the human being, who was initially in the middle of the food chain, has suddenly propelled himself to its top. This fast and spectacular change, has generated unprecedented consequences at the environmental level.

In nature, animals at the top of the food chain have had millions of years to evolve before reaching this stage, allowing the ecosystem to adapt. When a predator like the lion rose to the top, gazelles evolved to run faster and hyenas to cooperate better.

But when a species moves from the middle to the top so quickly, the ecosystem does not have time to adapt, creating a disequilibrium.

The reason for this sudden change is linked to the development of the human brain and what is called the Cognitive Revolution. It is at this time that human beings developed new ways of thinking and communicating by using complex languages.

They became able to collaborate, to share their knowledge and to develop new technologies. During this period (70'000 and 30'000 years) we find the first evidence of trade, religion, the creation of tools such as boats, bows and arrows, oil lamps, etc.

Although other species can use language, the complexity of human language has the characteristic of conveying information about things that do not exist. This allowed us to unite around common goals and beliefs. (Harari, 2014)

At different times in human history, societies have evolved and collapsed due to overgrowth resulting in economic, social and environmental crises. (Cline, 2014)

Today's society has evolved again to a critical point, with several major events. First with the industrial revolution (1773), then with the development of computer science, until recently with technologies such as artificial intelligence (machine learning) and blockchain for example.

As a society grows, it becomes more complex because more knowledge is created. It becomes more and more complicated to have a global vision of the world around us, because in a way, what we know is established on a form of knowledge that we don't really understand.

Companies and even states are competing in the innovation race, leading to the constant evolution of technologies and the exponential growth of society and human capacities. The resulting societal transformations bring serious risks of disruption. (Lourdin, 2019)

This paradigm shift has an impact on all areas of society, at the cultural, social and professional levels. The Internet is fundamentally based on the broad participation of its users. Without this participation, it cannot reach its potential. Due to the economic incentives of today's society, the centralization of knowledge and technology, particularly due to the patent system, (and the actual internet centralized data storage system) creates a gap between the population and large corporations. In other words, the opposition between producers and consumers.

This gap threatens democracy and citizens' freedoms and disempowers them in the use of technologies. According to Bernard Stiegler (2013), industrial expansion leads to proletarianization : "Today, people learn skills but no longer learn knowledge."

Consumers, from whom responsibility has been taken away, become dependent on the services they consume. The outsourcing of knowledge can be observed at all levels of society, especially at the professional level. In companies, skills are applied but knowledge is being lost. Scientists specialize ever more narrowly, but they no longer know the base history of their discipline (i.e. computer scientists don't learn the basics like the history of open source, etc.). (Bernard Stiegler, 2013)

This leads to a strong decrease of motivation, like we can see in studies made by the American Psychological Association (American Psychological Association, 2021), people become incurious, they work only by impulse because they are afraid to lose their jobs.

In a world dominated by digital technology, two paths stand out. One is total control of these technologies in the hands of a small group of elites, making consumers dependent and powerless.

The alternative is to move towards a contributory economy, empowering individuals and reestablishing the consumer/producer relationship.

Problematic

«How to create and develop a model of Lab that is a supportive environment for the development of more sustainable lifestyle solutions?»

Methodological approach

When we turned in the Master's thesis template in October, we had formulated five hypotheses. These have changed slightly due to the evolution of our work, mainly on two major points. First, we no longer defined ourselves as a LL because we learned that in order to be named as such, there is a process to follow with the European Network of LL. Our first monitoring allowed us to situate ourselves in the grey area between an eco-campus, a LL and an eco-village. Secondly, we took a more general direction than a simple knowledge base proposal; we were interested in a real ecosystem, an environment.

Hypotheses

Thus, we can reformulate the hypotheses in this way:

Question 1: «How can a LL be a way to find ecological and sustainable solutions to current environmental issues?»

- We have changed the meaning of the question slightly and replaced the term LL by ecosystem:

«How can an ecosystem be a way to generate sustainable solutions to current environmental issues?»

Question 2: «Why creating an open-source platform that brings together all students' projects? How to facilitate the sharing and linking of plural knowledge in terms of substance (specific projects) and form (code, reports, product prototype, etc.)?»

- We changed the first sentence by replacing students by everyone and open source platform by the more correct term knowledge base based on the common information heritage:

«Why creating an knowledge base based on the common information heritage that brings together everyone's projects? How to facilitate the sharing and linking of plural knowledge in terms of substance (specific projects) and form (code, reports, product prototype, etc.)?»

Question 3: «How to create a functional and economically viable eco-campus? What principles and business model (BM) should be developed and applied to make the LL sustainable?»

- This hypothesis is similar to the first one but is based on the economic rather than the environmental dimension. We have replaced the terms eco-campus and LL by project and ecosystem:

«How to create a functional and economically viable

project? What principles and BM should be developed and applied to make the ecosystem sustainable?»

Question 4: «How to create partnerships with academic institutions, political and possibly other associations in sustainable development (fund scholarships, send students, promote)? How to make them sustainable? Why can the creation of partnerships be useful for the development of our LL?»

- This hypothesis is also related to the first and third ones, this time on the partner side. We replaced LL by ecosystem in the last sentence:

«How to create partnerships with academic institutions, political and possibly other associations in sustainable development (fund scholarships, send students, promote)? How to make them sustainable? Why can the creation of partnerships be useful for the development of our ecosystem?»

Question 5: What is the most relevant LL model for our project? How to manage the LL (conditions for a project to be accepted in the LL, charter, organization on site, supervision, disposition of infrastructures, etc.)?

- This last hypothesis concerns governance. As we have moved away from LL, we have slightly modified the meaning of these questions:

«What is the most relevant governance model for our project? How to manage an ecosystem with multiple stakeholders?»

Methodology

Our project started with an idea at the base and a land where it could be implemented. This is why we followed a different approach from a classic innovative design thinking process.

The image below shows the iterative process we undertook to develop the different WP we defined at the beginning of the project (see appendix VI).

The iterative process we have defined allows us to make the most of the multidisciplinary skills of the group, consisting of engineers, economists and designers.

Definition of work packages

Our work has been structured into 13 different WP. This allows us to subdivide a large project into many small sub-projects and each of them with a specific objective.

Setting up the tools and foundations for the project environment

In this phase, we created the bases that enabled us to work on this project. Firstly, it was the creation of the association with the definition of the statutes and registration in the trade register. Next, we were able to create an initial version of the website so that we could present ourselves and give contact options. Thanks to the new visual identity, the site will be improved and completed in a second version showing all the progress we have made.

Having a web server at our disposal, we were able to install various applications for project management and collaboration between all members.

Finally, we created a database and started searching for experts and potential partners for the project.

Research, analysis, interviews and feedback

This phase went through several iterations and represents the bulk of the work done. Initially, we carried out a lengthy research phase related to LL and eco-villages (appendix VII), including analysis of the

existing and interviews with experts. At the same time, we conducted a field study that allowed us to validate and modify certain hypotheses. This first iteration allowed us to refine the first concept.

A second major iteration was done to research the BM and the governance model. The research and interviews led us to the world of open models (Open Models Report, appendix VIII), which after much research led us to a big change on the initial concept.

The input we got from the Ideavox association and some of its members was extremely important as they provided us with vital expertise for the choices we made. The search for contacts carried out earlier proved to be of crucial importance.

Conceptualisation and improvement of the initial concept

After each research and analysis phase, the initial concept could be improved and it was all these iterations that allowed us to refine our initial concept and come up with a well-defined and structured concept.

In a few situations, we did ideation sessions (appendix IX), but these did not lead to the desired results. Indeed in our methodology, creativity is framed by numerous researches and analyses that make the concept tangible and concrete.

Implementation and fundraising

Finally, after the several iterations of the previous two phases, we can present a solid concept that rests on the validation of the newly formulated hypotheses.

This opens the door to the implementation to come in the coming months. At the implementation level, we were not able to advance as far as we had planned at the beginning of the project precisely because the two previous phases underwent many more iterations than planned.

With the current concept, we can start applying it to different challenges to raise funds (appendix X), launch a crowdfunding campaign and look for new investors.

Figure 1 : Methodological diagram (figure created by the author)

Monitoring & literature review

The monitoring of open models is probably the most tedious work we have done, and the most important for this Master's thesis and OKA in general. The complete report is more than 30 pages long. For reasons of length defined for this TM, we will summarize it in this chapter by theme, mixing a small part of summary of the literature review and a large part of personal conclusions for OKA. The full report, with extensive literature reviews on each topic, is available in the appendix VIII.

Open models monitoring

Introduction

The evolution of our civilization is based on knowledge and the development of new technologies. Today, most of this knowledge and technology is protected by patents and licenses, limiting its development and use by all. (Arber, 2009)

The emergence of open models goes hand in hand with the arrival of digital technology and offers a new relationship to knowledge through collaboration and sharing. The term open model is a general term that encompasses other terms such as open (source) software, open science, open education, open data, open hardware, etc. Some of these open models are already ubiquitous and are shaping the digital world, but they remain subjects that we are exploring and understanding, topics that we still know so little about in the midst of democratization and which are still in the process of being defined.

The world of open models dates back to the invention of the internet and was created and used by the pioneers of the internet themselves. It is a vast world and very little known today, because its use has been misunderstood and gradually eroded (and forgotten) by the economic incentives of the society in which we live today.

Open models are leading to a new set of approaches that are causing a paradigm shift, at least on competitive practices and intellectual property, coming with new but unclear BM, some speak of a contributory economy. Open models are some seeds of the digital revolution in the field of knowledge.

History

The history of open models is intimately linked to the evolution of digital technology. The first computer was born in 1945, weighing more than 30 tons, and it is in 1948 that the first digitized program appeared. The first computer companies based their BM on the sale of hardware components and the source code was provided with the computers. Therefore, the first softwares were "open source" even if the term did not exist. Computers were reserved for a limited circle of specialists who mastered programming and who were able to modify the software.

From the 70's, the arrival of micro-computing marks a new step for the democratization of computing with personal computers. This made the world of computing accessible to new users. At the same time, new companies appeared such as Microsoft in 1975 and Apple in 1977, who wanted to keep control over software. The code is progressively closed, the intellectual property starts to apply to the software with the Copyright. The source code becomes the exclusive property of the companies, the software is distributed without the source code in the form of executables. (Open-models, 2023b)

For moral reasons, R. Stallman decided to take action against the takeover of closed software and in 1983 he announced the GNU project, to give everyone access to a free operating system which would provide the necessary software suite to run a computer. He defines four freedoms for free software: the freedom to run it, study it, redistribute it and distribute modified versions.

He publishes the GNU General Public License (GPL) using copyleft, a twisted use of copyright to guarantee everyone permission to run the program, copy it, mo-

dify it and distribute modified versions, but not permission to add their own restrictions. Thus, the freedoms that define free software are legally guaranteed to anyone who owns a copy. (Stallman, 2021a)

R. Stallman gave birth to the free software movement, under the auspices of the Free Software Foundation, thus formalizing free software and its freedoms. In the late 90's, a GNU operating system called GNU Hurd was complete but without a kernel and was not made for production. Fortunately, in 1991, Linus Torvalds developed a kernel that was compatible with other operating systems and later became a free software known as Linux. It is thanks to Linux that today we can run a version of the GNU system and use a free operating system. Nowadays, Linux is massively used by developers around the world.

This atypical way of producing software and the philosophy behind the free software movement questioned Eric Raymond and pushed him to write a book on the subject, "The Cathedral and the Bazaar". It was at this time that the term "open source" appeared for philosophical and semantic reasons because of the confusion with the terms free and gratis. In 1998, Eric Raymond co-created the Open Source Initiative (OSI) with Bruce Perens to support this movement. The movement launched by the OSI approaches open collaboration as a more efficient way to produce code rather than a philosophical movement based on freedoms. (open-models, 2023b)

In order to distribute these freedoms to users, new BM must be developed. The benefits that these freedoms bring will allow companies that develop these BM to quickly compete with companies that limit these freedoms (Raymond, 2001). We will see later on examples of existing BM in the free/open source world that allow these software to fulfill their commercial purpose.

Figure 2 : Open model timeline (figure created by the author)

Free/open source software

Open source defines the right to access, modify and distribute the source code. Thus, it can be improved and developed in a collaborative way by the community of users. Open source software has the advantage of being verifiable and of being able to evolve according to the needs of the community and by the community. It offers more privacy and possibilities to users. This is exactly what we want to promote with OKA: projects that are accessible, modifiable and freely distributable by everyone. Open source is therefore an essential element of our project.

Despite a philosophical difference between the Free Software Foundation and the OSI, open source and free software define the same types of software. We will use the term “open source” in the context of OKA, because it is better known and used than the term “free software” and for the semiotic reasons expressed above. However, we will apply the vision and definition of the free software Foundation with its fundamental freedoms to run, copy, distribute, study, modify and improve. This means that we will consider as open source any software or other commons that fits the vision described by the Free Software Foundation and uses the copyleft strategy to guarantee the freedoms mentioned above. This is independent of any OSI or other certifications. We make this choice because we believe that the open source nature of software or other commons that is not protected by a copyleft strategy is not guaranteed in the long-term. This is essential in order to create trust in our knowledge base.

Open (source) hardware

Open hardware is the concept of free software applied to physical products. These products can range from an aircraft engine to a piece of furniture. At OKA, we want to help students and general users create physical solutions to society’s technical problems, starting with basic infrastructure (electricity, water, food, and shelter). Infrastructure is the Foundation of society,

without which we can’t even run a computer. We need to be able to share, use, study and modify the open source technologies developed. Free access to these technologies would allow people to collaborate and gain freedom. For these technologies to be used, we need to structure work around them and develop new services.

Open science

Open science makes it possible to benefit from scientific discoveries, thus greatly increasing the efficiency, quality of research, integrity of data, economic benefits, innovation, collaboration between different researchers and visibility of research. (OpenScholar, 2022)

There is a mobilization for open science in government institutions, although this remains slow and not totally open to all. Like Swiss universities with a new program in favor of open science within the Swiss universities (Swissuniversities, 2023). Despite this, access to information at school level remains restricted and not completely open to follow an open education model. Open science as described by Swiss universities wants to open access to scientific research only.

Some extremely complex and wide-ranging issues such as global warming, the energy crisis and the consequential economic recession, would be very difficult to deal with without global interdisciplinary collaboration. Precisely because we want to act and participate in finding solutions, our project will be entirely open to everyone, so that everyone can benefit from our research.

Open education

Just like the term open, each organization has a different definition of open education. They evolve around giving access to educational material and forms of collaboration to improve the quality of the material.

Wikipedia is a good and very well-known example of open education service. It is a free online encyclopedia

run by a community of contributors available in 333 languages. Anyone can access Wikipedia, edit and collaborate with other contributors to improve the content. (Wikipedia, 2023) Wikipedia is hosted by the Wikimedia Foundation, a non-profit organization that also hosts a series of other projects such as Wikiversity, a project that provides open education resources for all. (Wikiversity, 2023)

We see here a possibility to apply the OKA definition of open, as defined previously, to the educational material. If we consider the conditions where learning can happen, as a part of having access, the problem of providing access extends to other domains, such as:

- Building infrastructure (shelter, computers, etc.) (Pedamallu, Ozdamar, Weber & Kropat, 2010);
- Having resources to run the infrastructure (water, power, pen and paper, etc.) (Texeira, Amoroso & Gresham, 2017; De la Fente & Vives, 1995);
- Sufficient nutrition (Galal & Hulett, 2003 ; Black & Dewey, 2014).

Copyleft

Copyleft is a strategy encouraging the equal and inalienable rights to copy, share, modify and improve the creative works of authors (copyleft, 2023). Copyleft is enforced through a specific license, such as the GPL or Creative Commons. Authors of works can choose this licensing mode to allow the creation of communities that contribute to the evolution of these commons.

OKA will also use a copyleft strategy adapted to its needs. It seems essential to create a legal Foundation, where users can trust the openness and durability of the knowledge base and its technologies, by guaranteeing the users freedom to use, modify and redistribute, with a copyright licence.

Open standards

A standard is a type of criteria, such as values or

measurements, that functions as a widely accepted consensus among different entities conforming to an established norm. (Cellucci, 2008)

The possibilities of open models extend far beyond the software world. In order to collaborate and develop these domains, we need a common base that everyone can agree on and use the same metrics. This is what we call open standards. (Open Source, 2023)

Many organizations try to give their own definition of open standards, but there is still a common definition to agree on and many domains to apply them.

Business model

In order to maximize the benefits that open source can bring, it is essential to create a good strategy that involves the structuring, governance and BM around the software or commons. A good strategy involves community development, code maintenance and the choice of the right license. (The Linux Foundation, 2023; Ahlawat, Boyne, Herz, Schmiege & Stephan, 2021)

The freedom to generate money with open source is essential to allow the development and survival of the software or other commons. Moreover, a good BM allows open source software (or other) to compete with closed software. (Raymond, 2001; Stallman, 2021a) In order to implement our vision, OKA also needs funds to develop and support the knowledge base, different projects and technologies, as well as the infrastructure of EcoCampuses.

In the open source world, most BM are based on the service economy. There are various BM that can be used in the open source world. We want to avoid BM such as dual licensing because we believe that all features must be freely accessible by all to qualify as open source. From the perspective of changing the current internet and finding a way to get rid of third parties, a cloud service model is not relevant any more.

In order not to rely only on donations, we need to find an economic model that relies on the developed commons and on which we can develop services. To set up a service, we need an entity to carry it through a brand. This entity must take responsibility for the business around the developed commons, in order to create trust with consumers. This is the principle of trademarks such as Prusa or RedHat, which offer services on top of an open source basis. The service serves everyone, people consume that service, and the money that is generated goes to fund the common that enables the service.

Peer review

The peer Review system is over 300 years old and has been poorly improved since its inception. With the expansion of the internet and open models, there is a need to improve this validation process. The veracity and quality of academic and scientific content is essential to the development and transfer of knowledge. Open peer Review aims to resolve the problems of traditional peer Review, but its definition is still undefined.

In the context of OKA, it is important to be able to verify the veracity and quality of the projects implemented in the knowledge platform, while maintaining the privacy of users and content creators and at the same time, the transparency of the validation process. OKA identifies a trust issue in this review process, that could be improved by a transparent and decentralized reputation system.

Economy of contribution

The contribution economy is an ecosystem based on knowledge sharing and collaboration between contributors in this ecosystem. On one side, there is the non-profit with the community of contributors who generate content. On the other side, there is profit with the brands that offer services based on the knowledge generated by the ecosystem. The actors of this ecosystem are linked by a common informational heritage

where common knowledge is contained. The users maintain this common information heritage because it is the Foundation on which the ecosystem relies.

A community is an essential asset in the contribution economy. In order to gather a community around a knowledge base that constitutes the common informational heritage of the ecosystem, OKA must define values with which contributors can identify. Values create culture and the cultural framework must be set by law. Therefore, OKA must protect its values in its status through a legal framework.

In addition, OKA needs to provide an ecosystem of tools to facilitate collaboration. OKA wants to animate the community by setting physical third places such as the OKA EcoCampus model, where the contributors can apply the knowledge in real life.

Third-places monitoring

The monitoring on the open model allows us to better understand how to develop a community as well as the tools to build it. We also see the importance of having a physical place to welcome this community so that it can discuss, test and experiment with projects.

This monitoring report presents our research methodology about the field. It aims to enlighten the readers and ourselves on our research topics and the terms gravitating around them. As a lab, it is important for us to define this term and to find a grey area in the existing by crossing different keywords such as «LL», "EcoCampus", "Eco-villages", "Research centers" etc. The whole third-places monitoring report can be found in the appendix VII.

Living Lab

There are plenty of definitions for the term LL. However we found some similarities with each LL, which can constitute a general definition. Indeed, authors on LL unanimously agree that one of the determining characteristics is that they take place in real environments.

The complexity and multi-contextuality linked to real environments are part of the issues of LL. Whether these real environments are limited to physical environments or also include virtual realities is disputed. Since this product can also be a virtual one, such as a digital data collection system, virtual realities can also be the context of LL.

Most often, however, LL will take place in a physical location, such as a neighborhood, city, or other area. The great attention paid to urban LL underscores the need or desire of the stakeholders involved to capture the real-world context in all its complexity while assuming that such experiments, despite the highly uncontrolled conditions, nonetheless produce useful and transformative knowledge. (Evans & Karvonen, 2013)

We noticed that there are few LL in Portugal compared to their neighbor such as Spain. Most of them are located in different regions, so the risk of being a direct competitor is lower.

Moreover, [our approach is different from all LL](#) in Europe. Until now, no LL is built on a virgin land. They are, in fact, located in cities, towns and villages and are already provided with existing infrastructure.

Most of them are subsidized by public organizations, in order to develop the local industry. It will be up to us to create our economic model. Furthermore, none of them place students at the heart of the LL's objectives, in order to allow them to test and experiment their own study projects.

Finally, many LL document the projects they carry out, but few of them give the possibility to obtain precise plans, in order to generate an open library.

Eco-village

The eco-village approach is above all the apologia of an alternative, utopian and ecological world.

After several researches and analyses on the different eco-villages in the world and around Castelo Branco, we can affirm that these approaches, interesting on certain points, are not in adequacy with our framework. Indeed, a majority of these eco-villages advocate spirituality and religion, which could be perceived as a sectarian movement. (Hildur, 2004)

In addition, some ideologies are close to social-political issues. The common point we find with our project and the eco-villages is [the creation of an infrastructure from scratch](#). The majority of these eco-villages are initially land that is made available to these organizations, which invite visitors or new members to join

them in order to expand the project.

However, there is one important point to remember about eco-villages, and that is [hospitality](#). Indeed, the human and social aspect is an important condition in these organizations that favor exchanges between individuals, which helps to create strong links between each participant. [Thus, social barriers are broken down and people from all walks of life meet to form complementary and effective teams.](#)

EcoCampus

All universities, institutes and schools can become EcoCampus thanks to the EcoCampus program funded by the European Union. This re-certification allows to monitor the evolution of universities, which must constantly make visible their progress in the field of sustainability. (FEE EcoCampus, 2022)

It seems complicated for OKA, if not impossible, to belong to this group of EcoCampus in Portugal because our project is not directly linked to a university. It does not have any infrastructure nor belongs to a local university.

The definition and the actors of the EcoCampus have many points in common with our project. As mentioned above, [the integration of sustainable development in research and daily management through collectively developed projects](#) is a central point in our vision of the project. (Bossier & Verhoe, 2019)

We wish to solve current environmental, social and economic problems by inviting interdisciplinary students and providing them with a unique place, conducive to exchange and innovation.

The challenge of our project is therefore great, since we must create an infrastructure that does not yet exist. We will then have to think of it in terms of sustainability, whereas the EcoCampuses have had to work after the construction of their infrastructures to make them sustainable.

Research centers

Research centers focused on ecological research are developing worldwide. In Portugal, we found only one such research center. This one is focused on [ecological research](#) for agriculture.

These research centers carry out observations, research, tests and documentation on environmental topics in collaboration with the scientific academic world. They are good examples of what we want to integrate into our concept.

Conclusion

This monitoring has enabled us to clarify the different definitions of the research terms cited in this project. Furthermore, it allowed us to define the grey areas between these different terms in order to exploit the gaps. This gives us a solid basis to situate ourselves in this ecosystem and to define the framework of our project.

Our approach is similar to that of a LL in many aspects such as the methodology of open innovation, the integration of users in the center of the process and the inclusion of the Quadruple Helix framework.

However, our approach differs from all the LL analyzed so far. Indeed, no LL is built from scratch. It is the government that allocates them spaces within cities. It is therefore up to us to build the infrastructure and to define our own business model.

Our project has several major differences from eco-villages. We want for instance to collaborate with actors in the public domain, and we do not want to be a group organized around a doctrine.

However, we both create an infrastructure from scratch. The majority of these eco-villages are initially land that are made available to these organisations. In addition, eco-villages pay particular attention to the hospitality and well-being of each participant.

What we have in common with eco-campuses is the fact that they welcome interdisciplinary students and create places to live and share. Another similarity is the integration of sustainability into research, the management of daily life and the resolution of current environmental, social and economic issues.

After the various research we have done in this document, we have created the following outline which better represents our search terms, it also allows us to better situate our project around four main themes:

Finally, we have similarities with ecological research centres in that we work with the scientific academic world to generate knowledge by conducting observations, research, testing and documentation on environmental and ecological issues.

Figure 3 : Our four main themes (figure created by the author)

Field analysis

We started doing field research as soon as the project was born. In fact, in September, we took advantage of our presence at two events on LL (National Open Innovation Camp in Lugano and Open LL Days in Turin) to interview experts. This presence has opened many doors and we have created over the weeks a well-stocked contact base of experts.

We separated the field study into five themes. The first three are qualitative interviews with experts, academicians and students, covering the sectors of the Quadruple Helix. This represents a total of about 20 interviews with 18 different people. The fourth topic is a quantitative study conducted online with Swiss students. Finally, the last theme is an observation carried out at Ideavox, a third-place in Geneva conducive to professional integration, open innovation and citizen entrepreneurship.

Methodology

Apart from a few interviews conducted directly at the two conferences mentioned above, the interviews were conducted remotely, via Teams or on Jitsi, an open-source alternative to traditional video conferencing platforms. They were divided among the different members of the group so that everyone could participate in this enriching exercise. The majority of the interviews were conducted alone and then transcribed and summarized by the same member.

The methodology used for these semi-structured qualitative interviews was as follows: for each sector (academic, students and experts), a specific interview guide was created. This guide was used to prepare for the interview, to keep a common thread during the interview and to remember the questions that were essential for us. During the interview, a few notes were taken manually, and then the transcript was completed afterwards thanks to a recording.

In total, 11 interviews were conducted with experts, 4 with academicians and 4 with students. As the field study is an iterative exercise, we stopped around February for the purposes of writing this chapter. We obviously conducted many more interviews after that date and remain surrounded by experts and various stakeholders to keep our project on the right track.

In order to remain in line with OKA's values of transparency, openness and respect, an email was sent to all interviewees before this chapter was written. Everyone answered whether they wished to be anonymous or not for this chapter dedicated to the TM as well as for the report dedicated to be published by OKA. They were unanimous and agreed that their names could be published in the Master's thesis.

As for the quantitative study, a survey was created online via Microsoft Forms, with 50 responses from students in Switzerland and abroad. Thanks to the large amount of information it provided, we quickly stopped

the qualitative interviews conducted in parallel with the students. This quantitative study is representative of the sample and represents a quasi-experiment since the situation can change from one time to another, especially in these unstable economic times.

The complete transcripts of the interviews can be found in the appendix XI, the interview guides for experts can be found in the appendix XII, the interview guides for academicians can be found in the appendix XIII, the interview guides for students can be found in the appendix XIV and the results of the survey can be found in the appendix XV.

Finally, the observation was conducted on October 20, 2022 at Ideavox. We were invited by Quentin Louis Adler, a lawyer who collaborates with Ideavox whom we met at the National Open Innovation Camp in Lugano. We went on a Thursday to share a meal during the traditional Thursday night contributive evening, open to all. We took the opportunity to take notes and photos in order to include an observation in our field study of this place whose mission and values are very similar to ours.

Experts Summary

The purpose of our expert interviews is to gather advice from people who have experience in LL, open models or BM. It is also a way to possibly approach them later for collaboration, investment or other synergy.

In total, 11 interviews were conducted with 10 people. First, three are experts in LL : Fiona Zimmermann, who has been working for three years in the Energy LL Association, Irene Mallo, who has also been working for three years in the LL of the Polytechnic University of Madrid, and Stéphane Masserey, founder of the LL RedLab focused on energy data valuations. Stéphane got involved because he realized that there was a lack of innovative solutions today, and that the current «silos» BM had reached its limits. So he thought of open innovation to change that, while people were still talking about co-creation rather than LL. Fiona joins Stéphane's journey because she joined a LL thinking that it is the best solution to solve the lack of stakeholder engagement and user understanding.

All three agree that the notions of sustainability and open innovation must nowadays be included in every company's BM. Irene explains that her LL, focused on health, plays a role in sharing knowledge with users to educate them on the subject and make them want to share as well. She believes that new technologies like blockchain can be a promising way to solve certain problems, such as the responsibility of managing sensitive user data.

They like our idea of a digital platform with a physical location. However, they advise us that for our project to get off the ground, we need to define our target audience well. According to Fiona, ours would be universities and other academic schools.

Secondly, we interviewed Georges Saad, an expert in BM through his numerous coachings to start-ups.

He supports open source and promotes the notion of transparency and access to information in the coaching he gives to start-ups. He thinks that our idea of selling kits is very good and that it would have potential because few people want to bother creating things themselves. One of the things he advised us to do was to start marketing the assets we currently have, such as the water filtration system, and move towards selling products, which are more profitable than services.

Third, we took advantage of the many attendees at the National Open Innovation Camp in Lugano to talk to four people, who ultimately did not have much experience in LL. Each of them owed their presence to the presentation of one of their projects to the Energy LL Association; Juliana Gadelha, with her aquaponics business, Jasmine Bitar, with her carbon calculator project for ski resorts, Katell Bosser, with her multimodal rally project for a company combining team building and discovery of their city, and finally Lucio Kilcher, with his start-up designing bicycles with a trailer for goods.

Just like the LL experts, they all agree that today, sustainability must be integrated in companies, and that open models are very promising. Lucio adds that they are even more interesting if our LL receives public funding. Juliana specifies that her company wants to create an open database on fish and agri-food products to share their progress with users. However, they point out that social maturity has not yet been reached on this subject, and warn us about the possible reluctance of the industry or the dissonance created by the interpretation of this vast and still new subject.

Concerning the sale of kits, they also like it. Lucio thinks that we should try to produce as locally as possible and to decentralize the production in several places.

Finally, they gave us a lot of advice, such as thinking

about the remuneration quickly, being well trained on the tools to create a good collective governance, or watching out for the personalities that can sometimes take over with time.

Fourth, we conducted three interviews with two experts on open models: Simon Rossi, who passionately creates educational content on this topic, and Lionel Lourdin, founder of several organizations based on the contribution economy. Both work at Ideavox.

Lionel warns us about the disadvantages of the public domain, which he calls the drama of the commons. It represents a well of resources that large companies can tap into, increasing their capacity for innovation. Indeed, they can legally patent works found in the public domain, not by patenting the hardware itself, since there must be a notion of novelty, but on the process or methodology of assembling it. Lionel claims a sociology of innovation where contributors can engage and be recognized for their work: free licenses.

Free licenses are the second type of license that exist. Some are based on copyleft, a strategy, or social contract, that uses copyright. It has four freedoms, the same as for free software, and two obligations: the right to study, use, modify, and redistribute identical or modified copies, and the obligation to cite the source and original author. Copyleft also obliges a virality clause, or collective intelligence obligation, which forces all works that have built on a copylefted work to be put back into the same license model. Like copyright, there must be an entity that has ownership of the license, and these include the GPL, GPU and MIT licenses.

He also explained the principle of the service or contribution economy. He illustrates this with the 3D printer company Prusa, which makes the source code and plans for its 3D printers available and offers users cheaper printers through centralized production. Lionel defines this as a service, since Prusa makes cheaper printers for users. The brand has developed a real community around their open source service and thus

benefits from an outsourced R&D by the community. The money saved on R&D is used to reduce production costs. In addition, the brand now federates public trust. Thus, even if anyone can create another brand selling services on the same commons to compete with it, Prusa is hard to challenge for these two reasons. In summary, brands are needed to carry services and to take commercial and legal responsibility for a commons, and these brands are the label of trust for users.

[Lionel adds that copyleft free licenses relieve the author of the responsibility in case of problems of use of the product.](#) Without this, the community would not dare to share and collaborate freely, knowing that they would be responsible for the consequences if a problem occurred afterwards. This is where service comes in, as companies can become experts in the field and take responsibility for selling services on it. There is indeed a demand from customers who are willing to pay for a company to build the product for them, even if it is available in open source, and to maintain it for example.

Regarding the revenue model, Simon simply advises to follow the opportunities that come our way at any given time. Lionel completes by mentioning several possibilities: selling, implementing or maintaining technologies in kits, or applying knowledge in the field of education, like offering certifications on knowledge or on the database for example. He advises us not to rely only on donations and grants, although useful at the beginning to launch our project, but to think of a possible virtuous circle thanks to the service economy. This consists in relying on the common generated to develop services. These services then benefit the members of the network, and the money generated by the consumption of these services in turn finances the common.

Lionel points out that even though we are creating a non-profit organization, that doesn't mean that we can't make money. It just means that the founders can't enrich themselves.

Simon warns of the risk with open models. According to him, people are not used to collaborating but to competing with each other, making it difficult to establish a collective and contributive dynamic. In addition to the cultural barrier, there is also the technical barrier; there are not many collaboration tools that support open models. On the other hand, he emphasized the enormous potential for development and creation.

Finally, Lionel explained the different advantages of a Foundation compared to an association. A Foundation is a moral being that does not belong to anyone. It can be non-profit or of public utility. It is not subject to pressure from shareholders or the General Assembly. It is made up of a Board of Trustees, which operates democratically by majority decision. Above it, there is the supreme body of the Foundation, which governs according to the rules of governance established in the statutes. This body is subject to a public supervisory authority, which monitors that the activities and the money are well used in accordance with its purpose. This has the advantage of giving the Foundation credibility and reinforcing its position towards institutions and markets. On the other hand, the Board of Trustees is obliged to make annual reports, which requires more administrative work than in an association. In addition, the statutes of a Foundation are immutable. If we were to rely on the association, we would run the risk that in the future new people would join the association and change our statutory goals. Moreover, to create a Foundation, it is necessary to release a Foundation capital of between CHF 20'000 and 50'000 depending on the status of the Foundation. Thus, he advises us to think about a transformation of the association into a Foundation if it has money reserves. If there are no reserves, he advises us rather to create a Foundation from scratch by finding partners or participatory financing to make the capital.

Academics Summary

Four interviews were conducted with people working in the academic field: Jean-Philippe Bacher, professor at HEIA-FR and co-founder of the Smart LL, Leonardo Angelini, collaborator at HEG-FR and HEIA-FR and professor of computer science and technology in BM, Marie Laperrière, collaborator at HES-SO based at the rectorate and currently working on the HES sustainability platform, and finally Omar Abou Khaled, professor of computer science at HEIA-FR and co-founder of the HumanTech Institute. All of them have knowledge about LL. They all like the concept of OKA.

In each of the interviews we found similarities regarding the strengths and weaknesses of our project. According to them, there are different crucial issues when starting a LL:

- Creating a whole ecosystem of stakeholders;
- Agreeing on a common vision of all stakeholders;
- Raising sufficient initial funds;
- Sustaining the LL;
- Make the LL economically autonomous.

They also gave initial opinions on confusions or problems that could happen to us:

- The presence of two concepts in one;
- The geographical location of the site and the difficulties to get there;
- The issue of open models if we collaborate with companies;
- A less rich BM if it is linked to the open model;
- The challenge of making OKA attractive to students.

Students Summary

We conducted four qualitative interviews with students from various fields and levels of academic study. There is Aurore Walcker, a second year Master's student in territorial authorities law in France, Kenza Chahid, in her third year of a Master's degree at the University of Medicine in Lausanne, her cousin Noha Chahid, who is doing the parcel year to join the Bachelor's degree in Economics at the University of St. Gallen, and finally Matteo Vozza, in his last year of a Master's degree in materials science at the EPFL in the mechanical engineering section.

Each of the students has already done group work. What Noha was missing to push the project further was motivation, time and financial means. Kenza also missed financial means.

Matteo and Kenza complained about the [lack of practice in their studies](#). Kenza illustrates this by explaining that her internships did not allow her to tour each of the departments. She thinks that it would not be complicated to do more practice at least between students, by simulating patients.

Concerning the sharing of information and work, Aurore and Matteo say they are lucky. Aurore explains that in her program, projects are shared with the rest of the class when they are handed in and that nothing is hidden or concealed during the learning process. Matteo says that they have access to more or less all the research but must keep it confidential. Kenza and Noha express their enthusiasm about the possibility of [sharing their work; they like the fact that it could be useful to others](#).

The OKA project appealed to all the students interviewed. Aurore likes the fact that it can [help develop a certain group cohesion and share ideas](#). She would be interested in participating for the social experience,

because being in law school, she does not do sustainability projects in her studies. Noha likes the fact that there are a lot of people to meet and that it is in another country, allowing her to live a trip at the same time. She adds that students at the university often have a [hard time finding people for their various tests](#), and that it would be great if at OKA there was a [spirit of mutual aid and students were more willing to volunteer](#). Kenza also likes the idea of [mixing so many different profiles, and the creative side that such a place would allow](#).

However, everyone expressed cautions or advice. Aurore and Kenza, although both enthusiastic about the idea of communicating their plans, raised doubts as to whether this opinion was shared by many other students. Noha and Kenza mention the lack of precision at this stage of our project, and would need more details about the cost, the duration of the stay, the possible programs to follow on the spot or the possible presence of support people to accompany them on the spot. Kenza advises us to [be sponsored by well-known brands to give OKA credibility with schools or students](#). She also thinks that this project should not be financed by the students themselves. Matteo, on the other hand, thinks that there should be many infrastructures to attract students in mechanical engineering or other technical fields. EPFL provides many machines such as a traction machine or a 3D printer, which are extremely expensive devices.

Finally, concerning the potential of OKA for the students interviewed, opinions are mixed. Noha does not see any benefit for her and the students of this transition year she is doing because she is afraid that it will take too much time from her other already extremely busy courses. However, she thinks that at her university's Bachelor's and Master's level, it would have potential. The projects are more practical and human oriented, and are more often in groups. Kenza thinks that it would have potential for her training, both in Bachelor and Master. Indeed, many medical students are involved in associative projects. By the way, OKA could for example give workshops on the different ways to raise funds for their association.

Survey

Our survey received 50 responses. 50% of the participants are studying at the HES-SO, 20% at the university or polytechnic school and the remaining 30% are divided between various other institutions such as the EHL, HEP or ECAL. The field of study of the participants is very varied. There are three main fields : business and management (32%), engineering (24%) and design and art (18%). Most participants are in Bachelor's (48%) and Master's (44%) programs.

80% of the participants have carried out at least one project during their studies. **90% of the students say they are sensitive to sustainability** issues in all or almost all of the projects they have carried out. 80% of participants who have completed one or more projects say they are frustrated if they did not complete the project. 54% of participants have been unable to complete a project due to lack of resources. Among time, funding, infrastructure, know-how, skills and self-confidence, the main lack is time, and secondarily funding.

65% are interested in integrating stakeholders such as experts, companies and citizens in the testing phase of the project. 68% have already worked in an interdisciplinary group, 30% have not done so but would like to have this experience, and only one person does not like working in a group.

The differences between the expectations and the reality of the education they received are diverse: **40% were disappointed by the organization within the educational institution, 32% were disappointed by too much theory, 29% felt that the studies were not close enough to the professional reality, 23% found that the content of their studies did not reflect their initial expectations, and finally about 10% said that there was not enough support for the development of projects and that ecology was not emphasized enough.**

As for expectations in the professional world, 45% want

to find a good work-life balance, 18% want to work with a team in which they feel good, 16% want a good salary, 9% want to be able to develop their personal projects and only 4% want to work for their own account.

More generally, **the issues that participants are concerned about are mainly ecology (75%) and money (57%).**

All participants like to share their knowledge and ideas with others. 30% of the participants say they are ready to test their projects on our campus, while 20% are not ready or do not want to test their projects on the campus. 50% of participants cannot answer this question. The reasons they don't want to test on the campus, or don't know how to answer, are as follows:

- Their projects do not fit into OKA;
- They don't know what an LL is;
- They don't have a project related to ecology or sustainability;
- Portugal is too far away;
- They don't have the money to come;
- The project still lacks concreteness.

On the other hand, the reasons why they would like to test their projects on the OKA campus are the following :

- Safety and security;
- Ideal setting;
- Test to be managed concretely;
- Values and vision of the project;
- Knowledge sharing.

Conclusion

Half of the participants are currently studying at a HES, which, compared to a university or polytechnic, offers a much more practical and project-oriented education. The three most common fields of study are business and management, engineering and art & design. This data can help us analyze some of the responses.

Most of the participants have already done at least one project during their studies, and the results show a clear sensitivity to the theme of ecology. This confirms us how important this theme is for many people today and therefore plays a fundamental role in all projects.

We can also confirm a second hypothesis that we have formulated, namely that many students feel frustrated by not being able to carry out one or more projects.

In addition, more than half of the participants say that they were unable to complete a project due to financial or time constraints, but also due to expertise or infrastructure. This shows a certain need for infrastructures such as OKA, where know-how, materials and financing are made available for the realization of projects with ecology at their core.

The integration of different stakeholders, in order to approach a LL type model, is of interest to most participants. However, a good part of them say they are unable to answer because the LL model is still young and not very well known, so they do not see the advantages of this type of approach.

Almost all participants have worked or would like to work in an interdisciplinary team. There is therefore a real interest in wanting to work with others and especially in learning from those who come from another field of study since everyone is willing to share their knowledge.

Several participants said they were disappointed by the difference between their expectations and the reality of their studies. This is mainly due to the lack of organization, but also to too much theory and too little proximity to the professional world. A small part of them also say that there is not enough support for the development and realization of projects. This last point needs to be further analyzed according to the participant's field of study.

Confirming again what was said earlier about ecology, almost all participants expressed overall concern about

this topic, as well as about money. In these times of war and economic recession, it is interesting to note that the topic of ecology is even more worrisome than the others.

Only a third of the participants say they are willing to test their projects on our campus and half of them cannot answer this question. There are several reasons for this, and these may give us ideas for improvement to increase interest in OKA. Here are some thoughts:

1. Their field of activity does not correspond to OKA
We need to correctly target students whose field of study matches OKA.

2. They are not familiar with LL
We need to better communicate what a LL is so they understand the many benefits of such a platform.

3. They don't have a project related to ecology or sustainability
This answer is very much related to the field of study, but despite this, it is often possible to introduce ecological thinking into all types of projects.

4. The OKA campus in Portugal is too far away and this trip involves a lot of expense
We need to make it attractive enough for them to want to go on this trip. We also need to define what funding can be offered to the students (will OKA be able to fund part of the trip and/or stay, can a scholarship be offered to students who need it, does the academic institution offer credits for projects done in OKA, etc.).

5. The project is still lacking in concreteness
It is true that our project was still in its beginning stages, and we could not answer all the concrete questions that students had. It would be interesting to conduct a second quantitative interview once we have progressed and better structured our project. However, it was useful to conduct an initial survey to identify the potential that the students saw, the potential barriers and questions, and to integrate them into the project from the beginning.

Observations Ideavox

On October 20, 2022, we went to Ideavox in Vernier. This place was created by Lionel Lourdin, co-founder of the Open Business Foundation, who created Ideavox as a collective intelligence project. In this house, experts in commons follow one another to share knowledge that is conducive to the creation of projects that have an impact on our society, in a reasoned economic logic. On the one hand, collective intelligence commons are co-constructed, and on the other, an economy of services is developed around these commons.

The Ideavox project was first thought of in 2012. After studying the engineering and research side, the research was put into action and the third-place in Vernier was experimented in 2018. 2022 marks the year of closure and 2023 the year of replicability of the model.

Everyone who comes to Ideavox can bring their ideas to the table, share them and exchange them to create projects and initiatives that can then be used as common goods. Access to Ideavox is free for contributors who are members of the network all week, from 9am to 6pm. For non-members, the doors are open every Thursday from 12:00 pm until the evening, during the contributor evenings (with registration).

Many projects have come to life in this place of service to the community. It is a framework that is conducive to the emergence of creativity. This is possible thanks to clear rules of the game. They are defined in a legal manner, with defined conditions of contribution. It should also be noted that Ideavox is a public utility and non-profit approach.

Concretely, Ideavox is a house with about ten chambers. There are several rooms dedicated to work, with various machines, but also others dedicated to entertainment like music or mixology (mixing drinks and creating cocktails). The members of the network can thus make the place their own and feel comfortable.

The human aspect is very important in this place. We felt a real benevolence and a warm welcome. We met about twenty people, including Simon Rossi, with whom we have kept a good contact since then. They explained that every week another group cooks. We helped ourselves to a nice buffet and exchanged ideas about our project and theirs, and shared many laughs. Ideavox definitely plays its role as a creator of social links and transmission of knowledge.

We have met many young people on social assistance, sometimes with social problems or out of school, who come to Ideavox to take control of their destiny and discover the possibilities of the contribution economy. They can propose ideas and thanks to exchanges with other people who have certain skills and knowledge, the project can be realized in the form of entrepreneurship, art or employment. It depends on each young person, where he or she starts and how far Ideavox can take him or her in the direction of integration. Everyone can contribute to this ongoing initiative, while respecting their own convictions. The contribution can be financial, intellectual, moral or political.

In summary, we have a lot in common with Ideavox:

- The commons and the contribution economy;
- The non-profit and public purpose;
- The inclusion of students;
- The link with a Foundation.

Because we made this observation early in our project, it has greatly influenced our various decisions and particularly our governance model. Ideavox is a concrete and complex example of a possible service economy model, which has been very successful thanks to its benevolent values and its solid legal framework. Finally, this observation allowed us to understand the importance of integrating a spirit of kindness so that the place is conducive to sharing and mutual aid, as well as this complex model where a place is offered to the community that creates the common goods in order to meet and strengthen social ties.

Figure 4 : Front of of the Ideavox house (Guillet, 2023)

Figure 5 : Dinner during a contributory evening (Guillet, 2023)

Figure 6 : Garden of Ideavox house (Guillet, 2023)

Figure 7 : A prototyping room at Ideavox (Guillet, 2023)

Figure 8 : Another prototyping room at Ideavox (Guillet, 2023)

Figure 9 : Entrance of the Ideavox house (Guillet, 2023)

Conclusion

This field study brought us many positive points. First of all, it allowed us to get in touch with people who could give us a helping hand to access funds or potential investors. Juliana for example told us about a campaign she works for, which helps compensate companies that are involved in plastic problems. If we can prove it, we can receive up to 2'000€ per month. She offered to introduce us to the director once we had matured the idea and applied. These different interviews were also a way to ask for possible fundings or collaborations later on. Secondly, it was useful to make a first round with our different stakeholders, even if the project was still in its early stages. This allowed us to identify the potential, the possible restraints, and the questions that students, academicians, and experts identify, and to integrate them into the project from the beginning. Finally, it allowed us to get known on a small scale and to remain in our values of transparency and collaboration.

There were sometimes contradictory opinions. For example, Lionel and Simon talked about selling services, while Georges advised us to move towards selling products, which he considered more profitable than services. Nevertheless, we selected the advice that seemed the most relevant to us and put into practice many of the tips we received, such as developing the governance model before the BM or joining the Energy LL Association.

Concerning this last point, our application for membership was unfortunately refused on April 28. Indeed, there has been some changes in the strategy of the association and they now only accept individual members. We are not thinking of joining as an individual because they will potentially create a new network organization of Swiss LL that we could join with OKA (appendix XVI).

The opinions on OKA are quite positive; everyone likes our project. However, we know that it is easy to find

people who encourage us, but that in reality, it is much more difficult to find people who really want to support us. Concerning the ways of improvement, we regret not to have been able to make more observations, like visiting some LL in Switzerland or in Portugal.

We also note that few students know about LL, and that in general, few people know about open models or the contribution economy. As many experts or academicians have pointed out, it can be a winding road to work with companies. So there is a real democratization work to do. However, there is a real potential here and this is a point on which the majority of those interviewed agree.

Concerning the interviews conducted with students, we stopped at four students only, because their opinion was very similar to the survey and we did not see the added value at this stage. At a later stage, it would be interesting to conduct further qualitative interviews with students, which would also allow to provide more concrete information on the questions that students legitimately ask themselves.

Final concept

Background

Figure 11 : OKA timeline (figure created by the author)

General description

OKA is a non-profit organization that aims to support the collaboration and sharing of open and sustainable knowledge and systems, using a knowledge base and physical third-places.

Encouraging the use, sharing and innovation of these commons empowers everyone and supports the evolution of a sustainable society.

In order to do this, OKA needs to put in place a new ecosystem based on a new contributive economy.

OKA will be divided into three bodies:

1. The non profit Foundation OKA, which aims to support the ecosystem by providing standards and technical and legal tools to share knowledge.

2. OKA Labs, which aim to provide a model of physical places for students to develop and implement sustainable projects.

3. OKA brands, which offer services based on the systems contained in the knowledge base and take economic and legal responsibility for them.

Everyone is encouraged to integrate this ecosystem and use the knowledge base.

At first, OKA's focus will be to target students and integrate them into this ecosystem through OKA Labs. Students are the main actors in the dynamics of opening up knowledge and in the evolution of society.

Figure 10 : OKA ecosystem (figure created by the author)

SWOT

The SWOT matrix as a means to prepare our strategic plan and to adapt to our environment.

The internal analysis allows us to identify the characteristics of OKA. Strategic planning often involves new initiatives and changes in resource allocation.

Before beginning this planning process, it is helpful to know the current state of OKA so that you can make future-oriented decisions.

PESTEL

PESTEL analysis is a strategic analysis tool for identifying external factors (opportunities and threats) that may have an impact, positive or negative, on the association. It provides a global view of the association's environment. We have put forward six pivotal variables. These identify factors that can significantly affect the structure of an industry or sector and the success or failure of strategies within it.

Politic

Politics is moving for the environment as the time for finding solutions is running out. We have seen in recent years in Europe many pro-environmental parties (e.g. the Greens) gaining new support from the population.

Opportunities : Strong increase in support (economic, political and legal) for innovative projects by European countries.

Threats : It would be disastrous if the war escalated and became global.

Economic

Crises are piling up; energy supply problems, rising energy prices, the return of inflation, labour shortages in certain sectors, at first sight, the year 2023 does not look good (Le Temps, 2023).

Opportunities : In the face of these accumulating crises, the world is questioning the limits of economic growth and the «meaning of life». Other economic models can emerge and be accepted.

Threats : Funds for research and innovation are being cut due to the economic crisis, the risk is that we will enter a strong economic recession.

Social

The outsourcing of knowledge creates a gap between consumers and producers. The consumers become dependent on the services they consume, resulting in a loss of knowledge and understanding (Bernard Stiegler, 2013). This leads to a strong decrease of motivation in the social and professional level, like we can see in studies (American Psychological Association, 2021). The increase in homelessness is also a social factor to consider. Access to infrastructure and minimum resources is paramount in order to promote learning (C. S.Pedamallu, L. Ozdamar, G-W. Weber & E. Kropat, 2010).

Opportunities : More and more young people are studying and specialising in their training.

Threats : Half of the main shortcomings identified with regard to training are the degree of preparation for the labour market, as well as innovation and international outlook.

Technology

Technologies and innovation are evolving exponentially, the development and democratization of the Internet and more recently of blockchain and machine learning (AI) are good examples. Technological advances allow the development of ecological solutions, open technologies with open source hardware and software.

Opportunities : Development of sustainable solutions. Internet is a communication and collaboration tool where sharing of knowledge in a free and open way.

Threats : Limits to growth - Control by centralization - Closure of knowledge - Pollution and waste

Ecology

The rise of environmental concerns and the assumption of responsibility by human societies have legitimised economic and ecological rationalities, as explained by two leading figures, the sociologists Arthur Mol and Gert Spaargaren (2000).

Opportunities : Individuals are increasingly sensitive to the issue of ecology and want to work towards it.

Threats : This ecological approach is subject to political appropriation. People are more suspicious of brainwashing.

Legislation

Legal tools to promote information sharing. Alternatives to classic copyright law, with copyleft strategy that allow to use, share, modify and distribute a common. Laws in favour of ecology.

Opportunities : Existing legal framework for sharing knowledge

Threats : Most of these legal tools are unknown

5-year ambition

The challenge for the next few months is to build the whole ecosystem of OKA by creating the Foundation. Then to begin to build the first infrastructures to welcome the students. To do this, funds must be raised quickly. As the BM and the governance model have been completed, it is essential to go and meet the future

partner universities of OKA. And once the infrastructure is in place, to bind us by a contract. At the same time, the OKA website and its techniques and tools are being built and should be completed before the students arrive.

- Raise funds
- Developing the OKA lab with first student projects
- Create the OKA Foundation
- Get permission to build
- Register the association in Portugal

- Create the OKA brand
- Conclude agreements with universities
- Develop the open standard

- Conclude agreements with other brands
- Choose or develop technology for database
- Creation and of the community

Objectives and performance indicators

It is absolutely crucial to understand the interrelationship between goals and objectives and the actions or methods needed to achieve them.

With increasingly fragmented audiences and the multiplication of communication channels and tools, the need to equip ourselves with even more relevant and precise indicators, responding to the increasing complexity of our function and the sophistication of our objectives, has become clear.

The important thing is to set up a sort of «KPI hygiene»: that is to say, to start with a limited number of indicators that respond to our priority needs and that we will be able to monitor over time in order to progress, even if it means making them evolve over time.

We used the four families of indicators around which we structured our deliverables and were able to make a selection of KPIs: commitment indicators / business indicators / reputation indicators / and risk management indicators.

Engagement

- At least 2 projects completed or in progress at the OKA Lab
- The first core community begins to form, at least a dozen active members
- Quantification and qualification of visitors to our website (Internal NPS)

Business

- Raise at least another 50k to finance the first projects on the ground
- Start negotiating agreements with the HES-SO and the University of Coimbra
- Make at least two agreements with some of the 4 stakeholders

Standing

- Appear in at least one scientific or innovation and start-up magazine
- Appear in at least one online news item
- Double the current traffic on our website

Governance

The study of open models offers new economic, social and cultural possibilities. We have seen some business model possibilities with the service economy, the importance of the collaboration of all the actors of the network and the licenses allowing to define the legal framework around the collaboration. Indeed, these concepts allow a paradigm shift where the actors of the economic network collaborate through a common informational heritage allowing them to reduce the opposition between consumer and producer. The question that arises is how to develop an ecosystem based on these concepts and how to govern this ecosystem.

OKA values

To bring a community together and create a culture, it is necessary to define values around which people can identify themselves. Values without implementation remain ideologies. It is therefore essential to implement them in a practical and legal manner. (Lourdin, 2019)

1. Share knowledge freely to everyone

The Foundation of any civilisation is knowledge and a language that conveys this information. History shows democratization of knowledge happens through the evolution of technology. (Arber, 2009) Therefore OKA creates or uses open standards that define protocols (Language) and knowledge representations to build or improve this very Foundation. Fundamentally what OKA tries to do, is building with the community implementations of such standards and the tools to create knowledge stored in such systems. OKA will publish all information that it generates with a copyleft strategy, to ensure the freedoms defined in the license. Beside legal guarantees, implementations must also be open source and have features as described in the following sections.

Read, fork and merge

To enable a distributed collaboration a version control strategy must be included. That allows users to read, fork and merge back changes to the knowledge. This allows anybody to create copies and modify them. If the changes are accepted of an "owner" of a project, those changes can be merged back to evolve the project.

If a copyleft strategy is applied to the implementation and knowledge, user in the network can collaborate freely. For OKA the version control system serve as a basis for an contributive economy. (Lourdin, 2019)

Voluntary disclosure of identity

Accessing the knowledge must be "safe" for the user (privacy). This requires that the information sent and received can not be read by a third party (encryption) and it should not be possible to know in which location the encrypted data is stored (decentralization). No individuals or groups should be able to "know" anything about the users, beside what they are willing to disclose. This can be achieved by letting the user generates cryptographic keys locally, which are then used to access the network (self-encryption). Also user can create multiple identities and can voluntarily attach information to those Identities.

No centralized control

An implementation must not allow, that any user can interrupt any communication between users, restrict access to users and censor the information publish by users. Therefore the users must provide the infrastructure to run the network and encrypt their data with locally generated keys (self-encryption). This also leads participants to collaborate in order to provide the infrastructure and information. When properly done, the implementation prevents any part from shutting down or limiting the operation of the network. To summarize, implementations must integrate following concepts:

- No one can interrupt communication between users (decentralization);
- No one can remove published content (censorship-resistance);
- No one can change the published information (Trust-less);
- No one "owns" the network, all users have the same rights (Owner-less).

2. Encourage collaboration and education

Free Knowledge can not exist without a community surrounding it, therefore OKA wants to be a productive member of such a community by:

- Improve quality and trust of the knowledge;
- Create and maintain tools with the community;
- Supporting open projects that build infrastructure.

Also OKA will promote and educate the community about open models and how to apply them in the real world. The interaction with the community and projects will be defined in the OKA Community Standard, that describes the tools, licenses and processes used.

Create trust

One can only trust knowledge if it is independently verifiable. It is also

impractical for every user to independently redo this verification to know if the claimed specifications are true. A reputation system, that can be trusted and can rate or score different aspects of a type of information, could alleviate the need for independent verifications. OKA implies that such a reputation system is a basic feature a community must have to be productive, by being able to organize/filter knowledge and making informed decisions. But most importantly the community must be able to trust this reputation system. This is achieved by applying the OKA values to the implementation of a reputation system, to ensure the system is "trust-less".

Tools

Tools are used in every aspect of human activity, we need to have access to tools to be able to produce and share knowledge. The knowledge how to build and use tools must be free and open to everyone, as part of the common informational heritage. OKA will use, create and improve existing tools, that are used or created by the community and comply with the OKA values. Tools with the following features will be a focus of OKA:

- Improving and creating of open standards;
- Improve and encourage collaboration;
- Education through collaboration;
- Building infrastructure.

3. Support sustainable systems and technologies

The fact is that society depends on the ecosystem to survive and that the infrastructure and economic models must therefore be integrated in a sustainable way with the ecological reality. Everything OKA does is in collaboration with its community, of which the collaborative members of the OKA Foundation are also a part

of. Thus, in collaboration with the community, OKA wants to support projects that are compatible with the OKA values and with a focus on infrastructure.

Infrastructure

An infrastructure is the Foundation of any economical endeavor. Free knowledge about systems and technologies that empower everyone to build their own infrastructure is seen as a main priority for OKA. Knowledge can only be truly free, if the surrounding infrastructure provides the resources needed for the wellbeing and productivity of the user. OKA wants to support projects that aim to take responsibility of their own resource consumption, by producing locally. In the hope to create a culture, where knowledge is learned and applied by the customer, to reduce the dependencies from the producers.

Economy

On top of such an open infrastructure, OKA wants to promote a contributive economy. In this contributive economy, OKA creates and maintains sustainable interactions between the market participants and the ecosystems. Doing so by helping projects, that align with the OKA values, to implement services based on open models.

Ecosystem OKA

Figure 12 : OKA governance (figure created by the author)

The diagram above represents a prototype of a governance model, inspired by the contributory governance model, that we intend to implement in the OKA framework.

The knowledge base is a technological commons and is the common information heritage of our ecosystem. On the left, in the “non-profit” part, is the network of contributors with citizens from the private or public domain. They use the knowledge base to build collective intelligence and commons such as the “free” and “open” technologies.

In the right column is the market economy. Profit-oriented companies offer, through brands, services based on the commons developed by the contributors

of the non profit part. These services will mainly be the realization of technologies developed by the actors of the ecosystem. The money generated by these services can then be reinvested in the development of the commons. In our case, companies can fund the OKA Foundation directly.

The knowledge base will contain a lot of projects that everyone can access and use. However, not everyone have the resources (competence, time, money, etc.) to build it. In addition, there has to be a trustful entity that takes the business and the legal responsibility upon the projects from the knowledge base. That’s where the service economy is. Companies can offer paid services through Trade Mark, based on the knowledge of the database. This allows anyone to have access to

technologies through these services.

In order to manage and maintain this ecosystem, the OKA Foundation (here in the center of the diagram) will have the role of being a medium between the stakeholders of the ecosystem and the common information heritage that is the knowledge base. Its role is to impose the legal contractual framework, i.e. a copyleft license, between the different stakeholders of the ecosystem, the knowledge base and the commons that compose it.

In addition, the Foundation can benefit from donations or can also offer services to companies such as R&D consulting, open model integration, license management, development support, etc. It also offers support for the development of digital commons in the non-profit part. (Adler, Innovation law researcher, personal communication, 31th March 2023)

Foundation

The OKA Foundation aims to be a trustful medium between the stakeholders of the ecosystem and the knowledge base. A Foundation is more credible than an association because it belongs to itself, its status are defined and cannot be changed, and an advisor examines the accounts every year to ensure that everything is respected. (Council on Foundation, 2023) We must therefore define status that are aligned with our values and that convert them into legal requirements. In this way, our values are no longer a matter of ideology but of legal obligation. (Lourdin, open models entrepreneur, personal communication, 24th February 2023)

The OKA Foundation aims to promote empowerment through the transfer/sharing of knowledge (and information) and the development of sustainable and accessible technologies. It allows the management of a common information heritage, a knowledge base, and its ecosystem. It will be governed internally by its founding members.

The Foundation then uses its resources to support the development of its purpose. It will be able to fund projects of students, other associations, start-ups that meet its values and respect the terms of copyleft licenses.

If the Foundation is of public utility, it has the advantage of being tax-exempt on the donations it receives and the donors are also tax-exempt on the donations they make. Other wise it can provide services to the ecosystem, such as R&D consulting, open model integration, license management, development support, etc. (Lourdin, open models entrepreneur, personal communication, 24th February 2023)

The Foundation values are applied to provide models and tools, that incentive sustainable interactions between the ecosystem and the culture around it. It must ensure that there are "free" (copyleft) tools available, that empower the community to exercise a contributive economy.

It is also the role of the Foundation to maintain the attractiveness and the animation of the ecosystem and the actors with for example quality content, the implementation of physical third places and interesting activities. (Lourdin, 2019)

License

When an author publishes a work, copyright applies by default. To allow and guarantee the use, study, modification and redistribution of a work, the author can use copyright with a copyleft strategy to allow these freedoms. (Stallman, 2021a)

Licenses are in a way a tool to impose and enforce the rules of the "game". In other words, to impose a contractual framework between the different actors of the ecosystem:

- Between the Foundation and projects wishing to access the funds;
- Between the brands using the knowledge base and the projects coming from it;
- Between the community and the knowledge base.

In order to be able to trust the openness and the durability of the knowledge base and its projects, OKA needs to guarantee the users freedom to use, study, modify and redistribute a common. It is essential to create a legal Foundation where users can trust the openness and durability of the knowledge base and its commons.

Ideally, OKA will consider as "open" (source, science, etc.) any digital or physical commons, which guarantees the fundamental freedoms mentioned above and which is licensed with a copyleft type of license. Therefore, OKA must use copyright law to create a copyleft license that meets our needs.

In the context of open hardware, technical plans, designs, 3D renderings and any other information about the object are considered as digital commons. However, for the physical object itself, it is different. Copyright does not apply in hardware, the same way as it does in software. To protect a physical work, a creator would rather use a patent.

However, the procedure is expensive and time consuming. (Open Source Hardware Association, 2023)

OKA needs a license that has at least the following points:

1. The Information is free (price/conditions) for everyone to read, fork and modify;
2. The modification of the Information inherit the same rights as the original Information;
3. The information for assembling/disassembling/operation/maintenance/manufacturing (lifecycle) must be free;
4. The information of the manufacturing line and the design are property of the service, an can be voluntarily shared.

Business model

As seen above with governance, OKA's BM is based on OKA brands and donations. In order to strengthen the OKA ecosystem, it is important to have a value proposition and a viable BM. We will present here the economic model, as well as OKA's development strategy and fundings.

Value proposition canvas

VALUE PROPOSITION

CUSTOMER PROFILE

- Brand
- Students

Business model canvas

Fundings

The financing part of this Master's thesis is important, as we have chosen the start-up mode. Among the pre-seed capital that a start-up can get in the early-stage, we have focused for the moment on grants, crowdfunding, Angel Investors and Friends, Family and Fools.

Beginning of September: Launch of the crowdfunding after the summer vacations, once our website, our social networks and our communication strategy have been elaborated

First, we took advantage of our presence at two LL events in September 2022 to approach potential Angel Investors. In particular, we exchanged in Turin with Filipe Almeida, who has already funded several projects in Portugal. He asked us to give him more news when the project will have grown and really started. Today, we are waiting to finalize our business plan before contacting him again.

Secondly, we talked to our Friends, Family and Fools. We are fortunate to have a friend who believes in our project and who gave us the beautiful sum of CHF 20'000, as a donation, on January 25, 2023 on our bank account. He wishes to support us even more through the constructions or the various costs generated by the development and the construction of the eco-campus, up to a minimum of CHF 50'000. He wishes to remain anonymous.

Next, we also planned to launch a crowdfunding campaign. The search for a crowdfunding platform started a few months ago but we quickly realized that we were not yet ready to launch such a campaign, as we had not yet defined our BM and governance model. Furthermore, we had not yet defined a communication strategy and our online presence was still very small. Before we can launch a crowdfunding campaign we need to increase our online presence: firstly we need to update our website (publication of created documents, blog, pipeline and goals, new visual identity, etc.) and secondly we need to create

an account on different social media (Linkedin, Instagram, etc.) in order to increase our visibility and to be able to attract more people to contribute to the project. In order to reach our goals, it is necessary to have a large group of people participating in the crowdfunding campaign. Our Project, following an open model, requires community support. This community has to be built and maintained over time, and when we manage to start building this community, we will be able to launch the crowdfunding campaign with a better chance of success.

Finally, we took the time to create a detailed list (available in the appendix X of the different European calls for projects in which we could participate. Unfortunately, as we were at the very beginning of our project, we did not yet take the time to apply for one of these. Moreover, we are lucky to have six students from the Junior Enterprise of the Business School in Coimbra to help us in these steps. In our list, we have identified more than 20 calls for projects, four of which we have classified as medium priority and four as high. Among the latter, there is Venture Kick, which supports Swiss start-ups in several stages. There is no deadline for this call for projects and we expect to apply after the Master's thesis is submitted. The second is the Innovation Booster LL for Decarbonisation, which funds up to 15 decarbonisation-related projects per year with an average value of 18k each. We know the contact persons for this call for projects well and may start the process for the next deadline, June 5, 2023. The third is Horizon Europe, for innovative European projects on sustainable development between 2021 and 2027. There is work to be done to find the most appropriate among all the suggested calls for proposals and to find project partners. Finally, there is U Change, for any student initiative for sustainability. We have already been in touch with the contact person and . In addition, at the beginning of April, we were contacted by Alain Renk, co-founder of the Open Urbanism Foundation, who proposed us to become Contributors of the Innosuisse presentation file. Indeed, it is possible to launch an Innovation Booster initiative for our own thematic community and contribute to stimulate radical innovation in Switzerland. Already close to the deadline, he had almost

finished writing the dossier and asked us to support his application to prove that this theme would find takers. We wrote a small text in the same weekend. We are now waiting for the deliberation of Innosuisse.

Timeline of actions regarding OKA's financing

Figure 13 : OKA Funding (figure created by the author)

Marketing

Students

Academies provide a supportive environment for the future of society. They are often public institutions that are in contact with private companies (for projects, use of software, etc.) and with the state. Students have the advantage that they are not under financial pressure and that they can fail (on projects) without great/personal consequences. This allows them more creativity and risktaking, because they are not yet dependent on making profit, which is required in the industry. The students of today will shape the world of tomorrow.

Our marketing strategy is developed in two different phases with two different target audiences.

During the first phase our goal is to attract students to develop their bachelor's or master's projects on the OKA Lab campus.

During the second phase our goal is to develop and enlarge the community to start running our entire ecosystem.

Phase 1

During the first phase we want to be able to involve as many students as possible to do their diploma work in the OKA Lab.

The strategy has not yet been fully developed as it will not be put into practice for six months. However, we have identified two different approaches to reach the students.

The first approach is to address the students directly by using different communication channels. In the two customer journey examples we imagined that one communication channel could be flyers distributed in the school and the second a newsletter received by email.

The second approach consists of addressing universities and proposing a pool of projects that will then be included in the list of bachelor's and master's work proposals provided by the school. In this case, the communication channels are very different and it is more of a B2B than a B2C as in the first approach.

Phase 2

The community is an essential part in the implementation of the contributive economy. Once the community is created and animated, it will provide a new way of conducting marketing.

Therefore, during the second phase, the goal is to grow the community by attracting more and more contributors.

The next page describes in four steps how the marketing is conducted in the contributive economy.

1

Viral marketing

The copyleft type of licences allow to everyone that uses it, to benefit from a viral marketing.

Indeed, a copyleft type of licence uses copyright and thus requires the author's recognition.

The person who deposits a copyleft or who contributes to its development benefits from a good reputation in the community if his work is of good quality. Thus, each person who uses, modifies, shares or redistributes this common has the obligation to quote this author and this last one benefits from a publicity blow and gains in reputation.

By strategically setting up an ecosystem that allows the visibility of the created works, it is no longer the marketing strategy but the quality and the know-how of the common that is rewarded.

This is the ecosystem that OKA wants to put in place, with a reputation system that rewards these works for their relevance and quality (Lourdin, 2019).

Therefore, OKA and its ecosystem benefit from a whole community that speaks for it.

2

Contributive development

The community will provide a constant monitoring and review of the ecosystem.

This not only allows OKA to understand the needs of users, but also allows users to share their needs and participate in fulfilling them.

Users thus become contributors and participate in the development of the ecosystem by proposing improvements, new solutions and by participating in R&D.

3

Community loyalty

In the contributive economy, it is the cultural element that is important to gather a community around commons.

There is no community without culture and there is no culture without information sharing. It is therefore necessary to cultivate information sharing with values and guidelines that individuals can identify with. OKA doesn't own the community, it is part of it. If the community no longer agrees with the values or direction of OKA, they can fork out the project. This allows OKA to remain true to its values and to listen to the needs of its contributors.

Culture goes hand in hand with law. This ensures that the cultural framework is respected.

It is no longer through privatization and contract that people's loyalty is held, but through the fundamental respect of freedoms and culture.

4

Animation of the community

As a major contributor to the ecosystem, OKA must participate in its animation by proposing activities.

Setting up third-places is a real asset in order to connect the community, maintain interest and encourage sharing and collaboration.

Target audience

Target audience - Phase 1

Our primary target audience are students of engineering, architecture and design, as they acquire the necessary fields to develop the first projects on the ground (first infrastructures and the IT part related to the knowledge database). These are students between 18 and 35 years old who live in Europe, and who wish to carry out their Bachelor's or Master's work in the field. For the moment, OKA focuses on students from the University of Coimbra in Portugal and those from the HES-SO in Switzerland.

Indeed, these students are comfortable with practical projects and enjoy working on topics related to sustainability. Their objective is to make their project(s) a reality, helped by the project's stakeholders.

Target audience - Phase 2

For the second phase it is more complicated to identify a precise target audience because a community as we want to create it is composed of many different individuals and it is therefore impossible to identify a specific target audience. This is why we see two general categories that we have to target.

The first category is represented by people who are already familiar with the world of open source or, more generally, open models, and are therefore already part of such a community.

The second is represented by people who are not familiar with the world of open source and have certainly never been part of a community similar to ours. In this category we find our target audience of phase 1 plus other groups of people who are not part of the previous category.

The target audience of phase 2 will be detailed more precisely later as this phase will only be reached in the next few years.

Segmentation

18-35 years old

European Students

Improve life

Sustainability and open model

Sinus Milieus

Figure 14 : Potato Chart Sinus Geo Midpoints (Sinus Geo Milieus, 2019)

As a reminder, the Sinus Milieus group people according to their behavior and lifestyle, and not only according to socio-demographic and purchasing behavior criteria. Their opinions on work, family, leisure, media, money and consumption are studied, grouped and classified into nine mediums. This analysis will allow us to understand how we should communicate with our target.

Our target seems to be:

Experimentalists (6%)

It is the young, pragmatic and adaptable middle class.

The Hedonistic Rebels (9%)

These are the young lower classes, oriented towards pleasure and leisure.

Digital cosmopolitans (8%)

It is the avant-garde adept at experiences, open to the world and marked by the digital.

Stakeholders

During their visit to the OKA field, the students will benefit from the support of the quadruple helix for their projects : the academic sector, the government, the citizens and the companies. These stakeholders are also entities that have an important role in the realisation of the projects. It is therefore important to choose them according to the values of the association.

Academy

In order to best guide the students in the realisation of their project(s), an academic expert must be present at the OKA site or at a distance. This person will be the tutor of the participants, guiding them and managing potential conflicts within the working groups. As a university professor, this person will guarantee the seriousness and attendance of the students by following up with them on a weekly basis. During our field study, we spoke with a computer science teacher who said he was willing to send his students to Portugal and follow them at a distance.

Government

The government has a secondary but important role in this project. Indeed, the support of the municipality of Castello Branco is more than necessary to carry out the project. We have already made contact with the leaders who support the project.

Citizens

As for the citizens, who play an important role in the design and testing phase of the projects, it is essential to communicate well with them on their role. OKA's entourage can already be perceived as citizens/future users of the projects, and it will undoubtedly be necessary to adapt the typology of users according to the projects.

Companies

OKA aims to make students' projects a reality. Companies can notably work in this sense, by collaborating with the team or by mandating them directly. So far, we have contacted the Junior Enterprise of Coimbra, they volunteered to help us and is an interesting contact to make the link between us and the Portuguese universities.

In addition to the two targets listed above, to make our ecosystem work, which is similar to that of an LL, we have to take into account the contacts that have to be made with the four main stakeholders.

Figure 15 : Stakeholders (figure created by the author)

Persona 1

Martin

Character

Martin is an excellent student, diligent and curious, he is passionate about new technologies and subscribes to several specific newspapers. Alongside his classes, he develops software for fun. Her dream is to work in open computing models. He is an honest person, who is sure of his choices and who has strong convictions. He is still a bit airheaded and tends to have trouble disconnecting from his work in progress.

Age : 24
Field of study : Engineering
Family situation : Single
Place of residence : Lausanne

Objectifs

- 1/ Meet people to do projects
- 2/ Become a tech whiz
- 3/ Be more connected to nature

«In a real open source, you have the right to control your own destiny.»

Frustration

Never works in groups

Finds that the courses are not practical enough

Persona 2

Alice

Character

Alice is a smiling and lively woman. She is afraid of the future that scientists are portraying for the environment, but she is optimistic and tries to reduce plastic, packaging and travel for the sake of the planet. She is aware that this 21st century scourge is global, and that it is time to stop greenwashing and use ecology as a political weapon. A very emphatic person, she has decided to stop eating industrial meat and is very careful with her diet in general. Alice is a voluntary person and actively participates in voluntary and social actions.

Age : 22
 Field of study : Architecture
 Family situation : Single
 Place of residence : Milano

Objectifs

- 1/ Building a 100% eco-friendly house
- 2/ Helping others
- 3/ Leave as little impact as possible on the environment

«Take care of the earth and it will take care of you.»

Frustration

No ecological project

No sharing of ideas among students because of competition

Persona 3

Christian

Caractère

Christian loves his work and is appreciated by his students for his pedagogy and his frankness. In parallel he is an innovation consultant for startups, as he once created his own company in the digital field.

Christian likes to help his students to realize their projects and would like to create a test space where all students could try all the projects. He likes sports and getting away to nature on weekends.

Age : 58
Field of activity : Professor
Family situation : Divorced
Place of residence : Zurich

Objectifs

- 1/ Would like to be part of a LL
- 2/ See more interdisciplinary projects
- 3/ Offer sustainable projects to students

"Interdisciplinary communication is where truly great ideas emerge"

Frustration

Lack of communication between students

Universities are too politicised

Customer journey

1/

Alice notices a flyer about OKA that her university has made available. She is intrigued by the title and decides to scan the QR code. Once on the OKA website, she decides to apply for her Bachelor project. Indeed, Alice already had an idea, but didn't know how to make it happen.

This is great news for her and she finally goes to Portugal.

2/

Once you arrive in Portugal, Alice quickly gets into the swing of things. Indeed, there is a wide variety of activities and team building to strengthen the bonds with the other participants. She will meet her work team, with whom she will spend the next few months.

3/

Alice and her team work and innovate for several weeks. Citizen users visit them from time to time to contribute their ideas and test the preliminary concepts.

4/

To carry out their concept, the team and Alice regularly consult scientific and academic experts. They are also present to provide a framework and guarantee the smooth running of the project.

5/

Once the project is approved by the team and the experts, Alice posts the plans and research on the OKA Knowledge Base. In this way, other people around the world will be able to benefit from this research and improve it.

6/

The team, which is now close-knit, decides to create its own start-up company based on their research. They will be able to sell their product on the market.

1/

Martin was studying when he received an e-mail on his student mailbox. He opened it and discovered the name OKA. Intrigued, he read the whole e-mail and went to the website.

2/

He likes the concept of OKA very much and is seriously thinking about contributing in some way. Sharing knowledge is important to him, so it is only natural that he decides to participate.

3/

On the knowledge base, he puts his personal work related to computer science, and when he puts his work in, he also starts to see what others have put in, and by chance he finds a very interesting subject for him. Being in his last year of master, he decides to develop this software for his semester project.

4/

Once the semester project has been validated by the professor, Martin works several weeks on improving the software found on the OKA knowledge base.

5/

Once his semester is over, Martin learns that he has excelled in this semester project and decides to put it back into the OKA database so that everyone can see his work.

6/

Imany, a student at the University of Cairo, Egypt, discovers Martin's work and decides to do her Bachelor thesis on it.

Implementation

In order to maintain a productive community of contributors who develop hardware systems aligned with OKA values, OKA will encourage and support physical third-places.

Because of the importance of students in the development of society and the fact that they are not yet shaped by industry, we want to develop an eco-campus model that involves students.

In order to develop a replicable model, we need to develop a set of systems and create sustainable interactions between them. This set will serve as an open source kit to build infrastructure. By developing this set of systems, we aim to become self-sufficient by decentralizing resource production with smaller-scale but more local renewable solutions.

Concepts

To build an infrastructure that is aligned with OKA's values, three fundamental concepts are applied. The first is the profile, which defines the resources required over time. The second concept is cycles, which allows for the creation of sustainable systems. Finally, the concept of services, which is the interface between the infrastructure and the economy.

Profiles

To tell the system which resources are required over time, resource profiles are created. Those values are then used to calculate a system that can produce the requested resources. However, resource requirements change over time and to evolve the infrastructure to match the new requirements, resource profiles can be adjusted. This creates a new branch of the infrastructure, to safely implement the changes, which can then be merged and deployed.

Cycles

Cycles are the basic concept of how the infrastructure functions. Everything is modeled as a cycle. The outputs of a module are the inputs of another and form a directed graph. The goal is to create sustainable systems, that are beneficial to the surrounding environment.

Services

Services are built on top of an infrastructure composed of cycles and are the control aspect of the infrastructure. They organize, plan, develop and control all aspects of the life cycle of the infrastructure and its components. Services are therefore the interface between the physical infrastructure and the economy. Services that are private for the users also apply here, which corresponds to the primary meaning of economy, namely "the management of the household".

Software

The applications are a collection of tools, aligned with the OKA values. Those tools are combined to form solutions that manage the concepts mentioned above.

Knowledge base node

As defined in the OKA values, the sharing of knowledge is a core concept. To achieve this, a network node must be built to allow anyone to host a part of the infrastructure. Further more, to build a trust-less reputation system, more research is needed to clarify the exact requirements. OKA will use the SAFE Network as a starting point to research decentralized hosting and a trust-less reputation system.

Graphical user interface

The part of an implementation that faces the user is a "smart home" application where all the data is gathered and all the modules are controlled. It is the central brain of an infrastructure. Everything is visualized and managed.

First OKA Lab

The first campus will be located in the center of Portugal, near Castelo Branco, where we have access to 10 hectares of land.

Currently, the land contains some temporary infrastructure, a small permaculture agricultural area and several water points. The land is self-sufficient in electricity thanks to solar panels and in drinking water thanks to the water retention and a water filtration system.

That space will allow us to develop a prototype of a self-sufficient OKA Lab that will serve as a place for living, research, testing and exchange for the students. This prototype aims to validate the Lab model and the set of systems. When the model is validated, this model can be applied to other lands.

Before being able to host students to develop their ideas, we need a minimum of infrastructure. Therefore, the first step is to find students with the right field of study that could carry out the development of the basic infrastructure.

The first competences needed are the following:

- [Architects](#);
- [Biochemists](#);
- [Civil engineers](#);
- [Geochemists](#);
- [Mechanical engineers](#);
- [Software developers](#).

OKA already has started working on projects internally and with students, to find solutions to the basic needs like: Energy, Shelter, Food and Water.

1. Energy

Energy is the fundamental resource which everything is dependent. Must therefore be a priority from the start. We focus on bio-fuels to try to meet our energy needs.

Methanol

Methanol is a bio fuel that can be produced out of wood and do not compete with the food production. It is used today on a large scale and can be used in combustion engines. Further it can be used in fuel-cells directly, to generate electricity. A student from HES Sion in Bio Technology will realize his TM on the idea to use bacteriaeas to pre-ferment the wood, so it can be easier transformed into methanol.

Hydrothermal carbonization

With this process a variety of products can be produced, by using carbon based materials, like plastics and human waste. One of those products are hydrocarbons, which form the base of many types of fuels. Further charcoal and phosphorous to be used in fertilizer.

2. Shelter

To provide shelter we want to work with students to plan the housing and build the materials needed for construction.

Architecture

We are currently discussing with architecture students in Lugano and Coimbra, in order to develop the architectural plan and the design of the site. This would be a collaboration between Swiss and Portuguese students and could make the object of a TM for them.

Geopolymer

Geopolymer cement is a binding material that offers a more ecological and efficient alternative to Portland cement (classical cement). Geopolymer thus allows to obtain an ecological, efficient and easy to produce construction material. (Geopolymer Institute, 2006) In order to produce artisanal geopolymer, the first step is to be able to calcine clay (in powder form) at a temperature between 650 and 800 degrees for 4 to 6 hours, according to the book "Geopolymer Chemistry" (Davidovits, 2020).

OKA wants to support research, to verify the feasibility of using local produced fuels to produce geopolymer locally.

3. Nutrition

The infrastructure aims to produce the nutrients (food and water), that are needed for the wellbeing of the people in the Lab, as much as possible locally.

Food production

We mix open hardware for automation with permaculture concepts, to achieve low footprints and high efficiencies. The goal is to create simple and automated solutions for food production on multiple scales, indoor and outdoor.

Water filter (Showerloop)

A working prototype water filter has already been implemented in the field. It is the bachelor thesis of one of us, in partnership with Showerloop. This water filtration system is based on the concept of Showerloop, an open source, low tech shower that collects water and filters it before using it, creating a closed loop. It uses sand, activated carbon and a UV lamp. In the case of the land, a modified version of this system is used to provide drinking water.

4. Environment

The interaction with the environment must be permanently sustainable. OKA wants to integrate itself beneficially into the surrounding ecosystems. Ideas from the literature on permanent agriculture are already being applied in the field.

Water retention

Water retention systems are the base for the water management in our infrastructure. Improving the ground water table and minimize soil erosions are just two of many benefits that retaining water brings. Essentially it's about slowing down the momentum the water carries, to give it more time to sink into the soil, thus reducing erosion.

Reforestation

Spaces must be retained to preserve and nurture the natural state of the ecosystem. This is done by reforestation and renaturalization and provides natural habitats for life and also builds up humus layers that are destroyed by human activity.

Carbon sequestration

Burning biomass to ash is a major problem for the climate. On the land, we already use a low-tech form of pyrolysis to create bio-carbon, which is then mixed with soil and compost.

Design

OKA's visual identity is its graphic identity card, which allows us to recognize it, sometimes without even reading its name. The visual identity includes the name, the logo design, the colors, the typography, the signs, the layout. All these elements are included and kept in a document, the graphic charter, which allows them to be used identically on the various communication media (website, press kit, letterhead, packaging...). The visual identity must represent OKA's activity, its values, its image, its mission, its commitment. It must also be adapted to the target audience, according to its age or category. If the visual identity must be timeless, it can nevertheless be the object, if need be, of a rejuvenation or even a total change.

Graphical charter

The graphic charter defines the visual identity of the project and therefore of OKA. It sets out the rules to follow for the entire design (typography, colors and shapes). You will find the researches in the appendix XVIII.

Logo

The house of the community, the one that brings people together.

The ecosystem around the house symbolized by a dome. This shape also reminds us of the eternal and the union

Technology that takes root and flows from the knowledge of the house

Declined logo

Oka's visual identity is powerful, young and innovative. Far from clichés, the main colors used do not draw on green, but rather on dynamic shades.

Colours

Electrical blue

Candy Pink

Red-orange

Light blue

Magenta

Water green

Typo

Akkurat Light

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
Z1234567890&é“(§è!çà)-_`^`\$*ù
%£`+=/:.;?,><@#

Akkurat Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ1
234567890&é“(§è!çà)-_`^`\$*ù%£`+
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Renens T

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ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
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Illustrations

Inspired by the colors and the graphic environment of OKA, illustrations have been made to illustrate the website. The image that we wish to convey is that of an imaginary world, mixing technology and nature where the human finds its place.

These were made with paint, then edited on Photoshop. You will find in the appendix XIX, the complete file on the illustrations.

Engineering

This chapter deals with the implementation that directly concern engineering. This mainly includes the IT part, i.e. the creation of the association's presentation website and the implementation of the project management tools, and all the work done on the ground in Portugal.

Before the two conferences in Turin and Lugano, we decided to create a small showcase site so that we could present our project. Together with the website, we created business cards so that we could share our contact details and allow access to the website via a QR code.

In addition to the website, several applications were implemented on the web server that allowed us to better manage the whole project.

Server management

Hosting provider

The choice of hosting provider was made on the basis of 3 criteria: security, ecology and localisation.

Firstly, the hosting service must offer an excellent level of security, this is important to protect our data and possibly those of our users when implementing the Alexandria library.

In order to comply with the ethics and ideology of our association, the hosting service must be as environmentally friendly as possible, so it must use renewable energy and have as little CO2 impact as possible.

Finally, the location should ideally be in Europe or even better in Switzerland, since the first contacts and search for partners take place in Switzerland and the closer the hosting service is to the user, the faster access to the site will be. Likewise for us, who will be using several web applications on this server, if it is closer the page loading time will be shorter.

After some research, we chose to subscribe via Infomaniak.

Infomaniak defines itself as an ethical and independent company, data is treated in accordance with the RGPD and privacy. Infomaniak is certified with ISO 27001 which ensures end-to-end control of its services to guarantee data security and confidentiality. The cloud they offer is 100% sovereign, therefore designed and managed in-house with data centres in Geneva and Winthertur.

The energy used to power the datacentres is 100% renewable and certified. All their data centres do not use climate control and therefore consume significantly less energy. Finally, CO2 offsetting is 200%.

Infomaniak is certified according to ISO 14001 and 50001. (Infomaniak, 2023)

Furthermore, some of us have been using this hosting service for several years now and we are very satisfied with it.

Domain name

The choice of domain name is very important as it plays a key role in how the site is indexed on search engines and how our customers and users can easily find it.

After several discussions with members of the association, we decided to use the abbreviation OKA. The full name would be too long and we would have a far too complicated URL.

For the Top Level Domain (TLD) we looked at two different possibilities, namely .ch and .org.

.ch TLDs are generally more expensive and we preferred a TLD that did not define a precise location, for these two reasons we chose to use .org.

Since oka.org is very short and its price is far too high (several thousand francs), we chose a slightly longer domain name, namely okalab.org.

okalab.org

Web site

Version 1

The first version of the site was designed and developed quickly before the two conferences in Lugano and Turin to be simply a showcase site with some information about our project and a contact form. In fact, at this stage of the project, we had not yet created our visual entity and it is therefore pointless to spend too much time on a site that will have to be modified later anyway.

The structure of the site is therefore very simple and comprises the following pages:

- Homepage
 - What is OKA ?
 - Why ?
 - Who is it for ?
 - Short-term objectives
- LL
- Contact

The site was developed using the CMS Wordpress. This choice is due to the fact that not all the members of the association have knowledge in the world of the web, and to allow better management by all, a CMS such as Wordpress is the best solution. It allows simple changes to be made via drag-and-drop interfaces, without the need to use code.

We have chosen to use the Astra template (Astra, 2023) and to create a theme-child so that we can further customise the template according to our needs. In fact, by adding a few lines of code, it is possible to customise the site much more and create something unique that represents us.

The site is accessible at the following address:

<https://www.okalab.org>

Version 1

Given all the progress we have made during the project, the current showcase site no longer accurately represents our project but only describes the basic outlines. For this reason, we are implementing a second version of the site which will be much more detailed and include more information and functionality.

Due to lack of time and a low prioritisation, the second version will only be put online after the master work has been delivered but before the oral defense.

In addition to a better description of the project as it stands at present (hence a change in content), essentially the first functionalities and pages that will be added are as follows:

- Blog with news of the project so as to give a follow-up to interested people
- A first partial version of the Alexandria library
- Pictures and videos of the site
- Crowdfunding
- Team description
- Page containing all reports produced
- Partners
- Pipeline for the coming months / years

The text in the first version will be readjusted to follow the developments we have made and correctly represent who we are and our project.

Email addresses

Having a proprietary domain (okalab.org) we have the possibility to create email addresses linked to the association.

Initially we created the email info@okalab.org, this email is the direct contact email of the association to which all members have access.

Thanks to this email on our website, we were contacted by potential investors and collaborators interested in our project.

In the coming weeks, a personal email to each member of the association will be created under the format first-name.lastname@okalab.org.

SEO

SEO is an essential component when developing a website. One has to take into account how Google's algorithms work and build the site so that the algorithm can recognize it and propose it in the first search options.

In concrete terms, this means making a lot of use of keywords that could be used in the search and having them appear early in the texts, writing unique and quality titles that contain the correct keywords, and making good use of certain HTML tags (such as alt text for images, meta description tags, ...).

Another fundamental aspect that Google takes into account is the loading speed of pages, the faster this is, the better the site will be ranked, allowing it to be shown in front of other sites. In order to reduce the loading speed, it is very important to optimise images in order to reduce their size.

Finally, we registered the site on Google Search console to obtain information on the current status of the site and to have data on search engine impressions and clicks on it. It also makes it possible to request

indexation without having to wait for Google to perform a general scan and find the site.

Figure 16 : PageSpeed Insight for okalab.org

Figure 17 : Google Search Console for okalab.org

Google My Business

Again in order to improve our presence on the Google search engine, we have created a business on Google My Business, which allows the Foundation to be shown in an additional rectangle that appears in addition to searches on the right-hand side and is therefore highly visible and in the first position.

Currently we have not yet verified the address of the business as it is located at the home address of one of our members and for privacy reasons we have preferred to keep it hidden for the time being. In the coming months, this subject will be dealt with and we will be able to verify the business on Google My Business.

Other tools

Project management tool

In order to manage the Project in the best possible way, we chose to use a web management app. This allows us to better plan what needs to be done, especially since we are working in 2 different places, 2 people in Portugal and 3 in Switzerland.

To respect the ethics of our association, we chose to use an open source application, and after some research we opted for Leantime. Leantime is an open-source project management system and can therefore be installed on our server hosted by infomaniak. This allows us sole and direct control over the application without third parties having control over our data.

The application has been installed on a sub-domain (leantime.okalab.org) and each member has access via a personal account.

Cloud storage

In keeping with the association's ideal and ethics, we want to use opensource applications and have full control of our data without it being in the hands of third parties.

This is why we decided to create our own cloud storage. Owncloud is an opensource online storage application that can be installed on your own server. We chose this application because it has already been used in the past by one of the members on a personal server and we are therefore familiar with how it works.

The application was installed on the sub-domain owncloud.okalab.org and is accessible by each member via a personal login.

This allows us to save and share our files securely.

Financial tool

Currently we do not manage a large flow of money, for the time being we have few costs as we are not yet implementing much on the ground, despite this we have received an investment of 50,000 Euro and we need to keep track of every transaction we perform.

That is why we chose to use accounting software. Also in keeping with our ethics, we chose opensource software that we can install on our server at infomaniak.

Due to numerous problems during installation and as a matter of priority, we have chosen for the time being to leave this application on hold and simply use an excel table. When the money flows increase and more control is needed, we will take the time to solve these problems and make the application functional.

The application has been installed on a sub-domain (akaunting.okalab.org) and each member has access via a personal account.

Risk management

The objective of this table is to prepare an action plan to minimize the probability and/or impact of negative events.

We are still at a very premature stage, and it is therefore difficult to identify precisely the risks that could occur in the future. This table will be constantly updated throughout the duration of the project, as at any moment developments and choices we make may entail new and different risks.

Being at an early stage of the project, the risks are greater and their impact too. We must therefore pay close attention to those that would have the most negative impact and be ready to react quickly.

We have identified 6 risks with high impact but medium to low probability.

The risks with the highest probability and high impact relate to agreements with schools concerning the projects carried out in cooperation with OKA, which is why we will have to deal with this issue quickly.

Risk	Description	Probability	Severity	Action to minimize
Acceptance of open models	We have seen a certain slowdown in the adoption of open models, basing the entire project on this ethic a rejection of this ideology by our customers would be a strong brake on the project	Medium	High	Communicating the values of this ideology correctly, through social networks, media and our platform. Creation and management of a good community
Projects/Ideas protection	All projects within OKA do not have a patent as they are intended to be open source, so they need to be protected properly	Medium	Severe	Choose/create and use appropriate copyleft licences
BM	Part of the BM is already validated by its market presence, yet its functioning in our complex ecosystem is still to be verified and may not work as hoped	Medium	Severe	We have to be ready to change our governance model to adapt to the market, or we can change the BM to previously developed solutions, alternatives are already in place
Open Knowledge Database	The database that is to contain all projects has only been described and there is currently no concrete implementation plan (technology, structure, etc.)	Low	Medium	Plan the implementation of this database so that an alternative can be found in a reasonable time if it does not work, seek external advice for the technology
Open Peer Review system	Being an open database, there must be a system to check the validity and quality of each project that is part of it so that it can be given credibility, conceptually we imagined it similar to an open peer Review system	Medium	Medium	Conceiving and planning the project validation system in conjunction with the database, and establish a reputation system
Lack of liquidity	Liquidity is the main resource we need to implement the project, it allows us to purchase the raw materials for the construction of the first infrastructure, pay salary.	Medium	Severe	We have a start-up capital, it is important to have an up-to-date cash flow to realize immediately if we run out of liquidity, start the search for funds
Transaction between Association and Startup	Since the association is a non-profit organization, the accounting and the transactions between the two entities (start-up and Foundation) must be carefully managed	Low	High	Define the tools for accounting and/or possibly outsource it
Other people's image of us	it is important that people do not see us as a sect living on the fringes of society, building a village to detach themselves from society and create a small community	Low	Medium	A good communication plan allows us to communicate what we really are and thus not be seen as a group of anarchists or anti-capitalists. Collaboration with all the Quadruple Helix stakeholders.

Partner	Partners are a key component of our project, it is important that they are in agreement with us and that the collaboration works properly	Low	Medium	maintain regular contact, be attentive to the needs and expectations of partners and try to respect them. Use copyleft licenses as a Foundation of the collaboration and we must define status that are aligned with our values and that convert them into legal requirements
Construction permissions	We need to build several things on the ground. In Portugal it doesn't work like in Switzerland, and getting permission to build is easier. However, you must have authorizations	Low	Severe	Knowing the legal rules for applying for authorizations and having contacts with the political party responsible for authorizations
Portugal / Swiss	Having the land in Portugal and the association in Switzerland can lead to various problems (e.g. difficulties in opening a bank account, being recognised as a public utility, ..) as the laws are different between the two countries	Medium	Low	Having external support from a lawyer or legal expert. The creation of a Portuguese or international Foundation could be a viable alternative to avoid certain problems
Schools partnership	A key component of this project is collaborations with schools so that it can propose different projects to its students.	Medium	Severe	Arriving with an attractive offer for schools and their students, creating a good network of contacts with them and being able to demonstrate the interest of our project. Impose our legal framework.
Schools fundings	Being able to send a student to our land in Portugal entails costs, these costs should be borne by the schools or at least a part of them	High	Medium	We need to be able to contract with schools and show the added value that these projects can have both on the student and for the school
Schools limitation	We may incur some limitations set by the school, such as the awarding of credits or the intellectual property of student projects	High	High	When negotiating with schools we have an obligation to impose ourselves on intellectual property as we want all projects to follow an open model, we work with them only if they accept to use copyleft
Lost of collaborator	The loss of an employee results in a shortage of manpower and could lead to delays in plans	Medium	Medium	Be ready to engage new collaborators
Construction security	Much of the work on the ground is carried out by us without the intervention of specialized companies and the risks can be different	Medium	Medium	Respect and follow safety rules and have an action plan in case of problems/accidents
Community	Our project needs an active community to cultivate our open knowledge base	Medium	Severe	Use the right tools, the right licenses and animate the community with physical place (LL), attractive UI and tools, events, etc.
Land access	The land is located quite far from major Portuguese cities and is not easily accessible by public transport	Low	Low	Propose a precise travel plan to reach the terrain
Quadruple helix model	This model entails several problems as it consists of 4 different stakeholders	Medium	Medium	Communicating with them and listening to their needs avoids misunderstandings and discontent
Licenses	We need to choose the right licenses and protect ourselves and our values	Low	High	Use an existing copyleft license that match our values or create one
Permissions and admin	We will need different type of permissions: building, use of chemicals, use of technologies for research, permission to host students, fire safety, etc.	Medium	High	Contacts, lawyers (Portugal, Swiss, etc.), secretary, etc.
Human resources	We need human resources in order to carry the project	Low	Medium	Create the infrastructure to host more employees and raise more money to pay their salary
Be accepted by the state (i.e Castelo Branco)	In order to get permission and be able to use the land as we want, we need to be accepted by the state	Low	Medium	Talk with them, sign contracts, prove that we will help the region, etc.
Get forked	If we don't respect our values and the will of the community, we run the risk of being forked by the community	Medium	High	Staying true to the values and cultural framework. Listening to the community, its needs and opinion

Figure 1 : Risk analysis (figure created by the author)

Conclusion

This chapter concludes our first step in the long journey that is OKA.

After eight months of research in the framework of the Innokick TM, we have built a Foundation to enable us to officially start the project.

Because OKA is not a simple master work. In fact, the project has just started.

Initially, the problematic identified was "How to create and develop a model of Lab that is a supportive environment for the development of more sustainable lifestyle solutions". Very early in the project, the notions of LL and open models appeared, leading to further research in these subjects.

Open models

The research on open models allowed us to approach the subject and to understand its stakes and its importance. The term 'open model' is a general term that encompass other terms such as open (source) software, open science, open education, open data, open hardware, etc. Some of these open models are already ubiquitous and are shaping the digital world, but they remain subjects that we are exploring and understanding, topics that we still know so little about in the midst of democratization and which are still in the process of being defined.

Open models are leading to a new set of approaches that are causing a paradigm shift, at least on competitive practices and intellectual property. New ecosystems and BM need to be defined. Open models are the seeds of the digital revolution in the field of knowledge.

We learned some key points that will allow knowledge sharing in an open and free way, such as the copyleft strategy that allow anyone to use, modify, share and distribute a common.

The contributive economy aims to reduce the

opposition between consumer and producer by integrating everyone in the creation and development process. The contributive economy includes a non-profit part, with a community of contributors who participate in the creation of common knowledge by developing new ideas and concepts. A profit part with brands that provide services based on this common knowledge. As well a common information heritage that contains the knowledge and connects all the actors of the ecosystem. In order to maintain a productive community of contributors, physical third-places where people can meet and have access to tools are required.

Third-places

This leads to the monitoring of those third-places, where we find the notions of LL, eco-campus, research center, eco-village and so on. We thus come back to this notion of physical places initially mentioned in our problematic, closing the loop.

The monitoring of the third-places allowed to find a grey zone between the different places observed. Thus allowing the emergence of a new type of third-places with the following properties:

- An approach based on the LL methodology with the integration of the quadruple helix that
- are the government, private companies, academic institutions and citizens;
- The dimension of a self-sufficient eco-village with local production of resources and life on site with the development of a local economy;
- The campus and research center dimension where students live on site in community, conduct research, develop projects and benefit from the experience of interdisciplinary and practice-based learning.

This third-place has been named an OKA Lab.

Infrastructure

We argue that a functioning infrastructure is crucial to be able to access the free and common knowledge available on the internet. Therefore we want, in collaboration with students, develop models for a physical OKA Lab, that anyone can use and implement according to the OKA copyleft license. And in the process start a community that develops any kind of knowledge in addition to infrastructure. This knowledge is protected under a copyleft strategy, so everyone can use, share, modify and distribute. Brands then can manufacture infrastructure systems, based on the free and common knowledge, and provide those to anyone through services.

Students

In a first step, students were defined as a first interesting target to bring these dynamics of openness and knowledge sharing. The reason behind this choice is because of the following reasons:

- Students are the future of society, they are not yet shaped by the industry;
- They have more freedom because they are not constrained by profit, the legal framework or the consequences of failure, as it is the case for the industry;
- Students don't have access to many places to implement and test their projects;
- They are often not motivated by their thesis projects;
- Most of the time, their thesis projects are not pursued.

Field analysis

After the exploration, we quantified our hypotheses through qualitative and ethnographic research. We then tested the qualitative study with a quantitative

study, which confirmed it in several points:

- 80% of students have already carried out at least one project during their studies;
- 98% are sensitive to the notion of sustainability in some or all of their projects;
- 80% have already felt frustrated by not being able to carry out one or more projects;
- 66% are interested in the integration of different stakeholders (Living Lab approach);
- 98% like to share their knowledge and ideas with others.

In the future, we will continue to conduct field analysis, in an iterative manner. We need to return to students in order to ask them about open models, to interview more students from other countries and to establish a list of the fields most interested in OKA. It is also imperative that we conduct more field studies also with the academic sector and more observations of Living Labs in Europe.

Concept and value proposition

The overall concept of OKA is to set up a contributive ecosystem to foster collaboration and knowledge sharing to empower everyone to be responsible for their consumption.

First, OKA defines values that will set the culture and the guideline for the ecosystem. The values will be implemented by the law through the status of the Foundation and the copyleft. The Foundation also provides a legal framework and open standards. But above all, it supports financially and through consulting, the non-profit projects that correspond to its values.

The OKA Labs act in the non-profit and aim to provide a model of physical places for students to develop and implement sustainable projects.

Finally, the brands are the profit part of OKA's ecosys-

tem, they provide services based on the systems contained in the knowledge base and take economic and legal responsibility for them. Thus, they guarantee everyone access to the systems developed and contained in the database, by paying for the service.

In order for this ecosystem to reach its potential, as many people as possible must be able to integrate it and use its principles.

The concept is innovative in many ways:

- Development of new BM;
- Integrating the contribution economy in a new way;
- Implementation of a new open model for third-places;
- Space dedicated to students to develop their projects and use these projects to develop ecological infrastructures;
- Establishment of an ecosystem propitious to knowledge sharing and innovation;
- A trust-less reputation system and a knowledge representation based on a type systems.

Boundaries of the thesis and next steps

A total of 13 work packages were defined for the master work and set the boundaries of the work. The work package which concerned the implementation has been completed for the framework of the master but remains in development for the continuation. All the work packages have been completed, therefore the objective has been reached. However, several improvements are possible and will be made in the future. The project management is a point that will imperatively have to be improved in the future. Indeed, the remote work, the different schedules of each person and the quality of the working tools made the collaboration difficult. Later on, open source collaboration tools such as GitLab will be implemented to make the work more efficient for everyone.

The next phases of the project will be the following:

- Apply for fundings;
- Build the infrastructure with the students' TM;
- Creating the entities (Foundation, OKA Lab association in Portugal, etc.);
- Get permissions to build the OKA Lab in Portugal;
- Plan and develop the OKA Lab model with master theses from students (Geopolymer, methanol, architectural design, etc.);
- Develop open standards.

Final word

The concept is innovative in many ways:

- Development of new BM;
- Integrating the contribution economy in a new way;
- Implementation of a new open model for third-places;
- Space dedicated to students to develop their projects and use these projects to develop ecological infrastructures;
- Establishment of an ecosystem propitious to knowledge sharing and innovation;
- A trust-less reputation system and a knowledge representation based on a type systems.

We aim to plant some seeds of a more collaborative and trustful society where knowledge is shared and can be applied in a sustainable way.

After this first phase of the OKA project, we have a better understanding of the possibilities and how to set up such an ecosystem. The road is long and arduous but thanks to our research, we have discovered ways to make it possible. The strategy is shaping up, it's time to set it up.

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Appendices

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